

History of the English Language

An Illustrated Introduction

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1st Section

**The Backgrounds
of the
English Language**

Backgrounds of English

World Languages

1. Chinese	1,000
2. English	350
3. Spanish	250
4. Hindi	200
5. Arabic	150
6. Bengali	150
7. Russian	150
8. Portuguese	135
9. Japanese	120
10. German	100

Backgrounds of English

Grammar Classification

- | | | | |
|----|------------|-----------------------|---------------------------|
| 1. | SVO | <i>cows eat grass</i> | English, Spanish, Chinese |
| 2. | SOV | <i>cows grass eat</i> | Hindi, Turkish, Japanese |
| 3. | VSO | <i>eat cows grass</i> | Arabic, Welsh |
| 4. | VOS | <i>eat grass cows</i> | Malagasy, Tzotzil |
| 5. | OSV | <i>grass cows eat</i> | Kabardian |
| 6. | OVS | <i>grass eat cows</i> | Hixkaryana |

Backgrounds of English

- **Vocabulary**: many similar words in several languages
 - Eng.: *menu* German: *Menü*
French: *menu*
- End of 18th c → Sir William Jones, Franz Bopp, Jacob Grimm & August Schleicher: theory of **COGNATES**
- Languages derive from common ancestor
- Languages split up → **cognate languages**

Backgrounds of English

- 19th c: **Darwin's** *Origin of Species* → Genealogical Theory
- Metaphor: Family Tree:

- Unaccurate theory: suggest strict chronological linguistic **evolution**
- Relations established between several langs.:

– 1) **Romance Langs.**

Sp. padre

It. padre

Fr. père

Port. pai

/p/ = /f/

2) **Germanic Langs.**

Eng. father

Ger. Vater

Dutch vader

Swed. fader

Backgrounds of English

- **Conclusion:** originally, one single language (extinct) → diff. varieties → languages
- 1st lang: Proto-IE or IE (**Indo-European**), area from Europe (West) to India (East)

Backgrounds

- **COGNATES:** words of common origin

- IE *bher-

{	bhar- (Sanskrit)	}	root of 'bear'
	pher- (Greek)		
	fer- (Lat.)		
	bair- (Gothic)		
	ber.- (OE)		

- **IE cognates:**

- numerals 1-10 - word for 10+10 = 100 (cent-/sat)
- words for bodily parts (*head, lung*)
- words for natural phenomena (*night, sun, moon*)
- words for plant / animal names (*beech, wolf*)
- cultural terms (*yoke, weave*)

Backgrounds of English

Backgrounds: Dravidian

- "old" languages of India, with about 25 representatives and **150 million speakers**
- very difficult sounding languages
- Tamil, Malayalam, Kannada, Telugu
- Each has its own script
- **retroflex consonants**: distinctive sound and are formed with the tongue rolled up to the top of the mouth
- **agglutinating** with up to 8 noun cases.
- once covered all of the Indian sub-continent and originated in the Indus Valley (modern Pakistan).

தேவன், தம்முடைய ஒரேபேருன குமாரனை விசுவாசிக்கிறவன் எவனோ அவன் கெட்டுப்போகாமல் நித்தியஜ்வனை அடையும்படிக்கு, அவரைத் தந்தருளி, இவ்வளவாய் உலகத்தில் அன்புகூர்ந்தார். (யோவான் 3:16)

Backgrounds: Sino-Tibetan

- very important language family, includes ~ **250 langs.**
- **Mandarin Chinese** (Putonghua) alone is spoken by one billion people!
- **monosyllabic** tonal languages
- Words are made up of single syllables: Mandarin has over 1600
- The syllables themselves have **tones**: the voice can be high, low, rising, falling; **MEN** can mean **gate** or **we** depending on tone
- Mandarin, Thai, Cantonese, Kam-Sui, Burmese, Tibetan, Manipuri ...

Backgrounds: Amerindian

- Amerind includes nearly 600 languages, with more than 20 million speakers
- **North America: Algonquian** (Ojibwa, Blackfoot, Cheyenne, Cree), **Athapascan** (Navajo, Apache), **Dakota** (or Sioux), **Iroquois** (Cherokee, Mohawk), **Uto-Aztecan** (Hopi, Nahuatl, Comanche); **South America: Oto-Manguean** (Mixtec, Otomi), **Mayan** (Quiche, Yucatec), **Carib** (Carib, Chiquito), **Andean** (Quechua (Inca), Guarani, Aymara, Tupi, Guarana). The Andean language sub-family (which includes Quechua) numbers nearly nine million speakers!
- common feature shared by several languages is the **Dual Pronoun**
- **Kiwai** has one of the most complex verb structures known
- **Rotokas** has the fewest sounds of any language, 11 (compared to the 44 of standard English)

Backgrounds: Ural-Altaiic

- about 20 languages with 20 million speakers in this family
- the **Finnic Branch**, **Finnish** and **Estonian** are closely related. Languages in the **Ugric Branch** (like **Hungarian**) are very different having separated from the Finnic ones around 3000 years ago. Hungarian's closest relatives (**Ostyak**, **Vogul**) are found in central Siberia.
- The majority of the languages in this family are spoken in Siberia (**Mordvin**, **Komi**, **Nenets**) apart from **Sámi** which is spoken in Lapland
- The Uralic Languages have many suffixes
- Country names in Finnish are difficult to recognise. **Finland**, for example, is **Suomi** (**Spain: Espanja**)

FINNO-UGRIC				SAMOYEDIC		YUKAGHIR	
FINNIC				UGRIC			
A. Baltic-Finnic:	Veps	3	Udmurt	A. Hungarian	Enets	5	Tundra
Estonian	Votic	4	D. Mari	B. Ob-Ugric:	Nenets		Kolyma
Finnish	B. Sami		E. Mordvin	Mansi	Nganasan		
Ingrian	1	C. Permic:		Khanty	Selkup		
Karelian	Permyak						
Livonian	2	Komi					

Diagonal lines indicate sparsely populated areas

Backgrounds: *Basque*

- **Non-IE language**
- VASCUENCE, EUSKERA
- uncertain relationship spoken by **~1 million** people, most live in NE Spain and some in SW France
- language has **eight dialects**
- Many regional varieties, but in Spain there is also a fairly strong desire for the **Batua** unified standard
- Some scholars believe it is descended from Aquitanian, spoken on the Iberian peninsula and in S Gaul in ancient times. Others think it is related to Caucasian, speakers came from Asia Minor
- agglutinative and polysynthetic

Adiós.....Agur..... Good-bye
Hola.....Kaixo..... Hi
Qué tal?.....Zer moduz?..... How are you?
Buenos días.....Egun on..... Good morning
Buenas tardes.....Arratsalde on..... Good afternoon
Buenas noches.....Gabon..... Good evening

Yes = Bai

No = Ez

Thank you = Eskerrik asko

I do not understand = Ez dut ulertzen
'the child fell in the street' = umea kalean erori
da
child-the street-in fall-asp is

Backgrounds: *The Indo-European Languages*

- originated in the forests north of the Black Sea (in what is now **Ukraine**) during the Neolithic period (about 7000BC). These people began to migrate between 3500BC and 2500BC, spreading west to Europe, south to the Mediterranean, north to Scandinavia, and east to India.

- divided into **12 branches**, ten of which contain existing languages.

- single **largest** language family, Indo-European has about 150 languages and about three billion speakers
- Over **1/2** half the world's population speak one or more of these languages: mother tongue or business language
- stretch from the Americas through Europe to North India
- Langs.: Hindi and Urdu (400 mil.), Bengali (200 mil., Spanish (300 mil., Portuguese (200 mil., French (100 mil.), German (100 mil.), Russian (300 mil.), and English (400 mil.) in Europe and the Americas
- tend to be **inflected**

Backgrounds: *The Indo-European Languages*

Backgrounds - IE

Langs.: *Indo-Iranian*

- Most are found in North India, Pakistan, etc
- derived from **Sanskrit** (the classical language of Hinduism dating from 1000BC)
- Sanskrit → **Pali** (the language of Buddhism), **Ardhamagadhi** (the language of Jainism) & ancestors of the modern North Indian languages.
- modern North Indian languages, **Hindi** and **Urdu** are very similar but differ in the script
- Hindi speakers are Hindus
- Urdu is spoken by the Muslims
- **Romany**, the Gypsy's language. Gypsies migrated to Europe from India.

सिन्धु सभ्यता भारत की प्राचीनतम सभ्यता है। इस सभ्यता का विकास आज से लगभग पाँच हजार वर्ष पहले हमारे देश में हुआ था। यह सभ्यता पंजाब के मोंटगुमरी ज़िले के हड़प्पा, और सिन्धु प्रांत के लरकाना ज़िले के मोहनजोदड़ो में फैली हुई थी। मोहनजोदड़ो कराची से २०० मील उर में सिन्धु नदी के तट पर है।

Hindi

Backgrounds - IE Langs.: *Balto-Slavic*

- **Slavic Langs.** confined to Eastern: South (**Serbo-Croatian, Bulgarian**), East (**Russian**), West (**Polish, Czecho-Slovak**)
- the Catholic peoples use the Latin alphabet while the Orthodox use the Cyrillic alphabet which is derived from the Greek, some langs. are very similar except for the script used (**Croatian** and **Serbian** same lang.)
- consonant clusters and large number of cases for nouns (up to seven).
- **Baltic Langs.** **Lithuanian** is one of the oldest of the Indo-European languages. Its study is important in determining the origins and evolution of the family. Lithuanian and **Latvian** both use the Latin script and have tones.

Backgrounds - IE Langs.: *Italic / Romance*

- languages are all derived from **Latin**
- alphabet (derived from the Greek alphabet) is used by many languages of the world.
- **Italian** and **Portuguese** are the closest, **French** has moved farthest from Latin in pronunciation, **Romanian** has picked up Slavic influences, **Spanish** has been influenced by Arabic, **Romansh** is a minority language in Switzerland, **Provincial** and **Catalan** are closely related languages spoken in the south of France and the north-east of Spain. Extinct languages include **Dalmatian**, **Oscan**, **Faliscan**, **Sabine** and **Umbrian**.
- Latin had three genders and at least six cases for its nouns and a Subject-Object-Verb sentence structure

Backgrounds - IE Langs.: *Celtic*

- originated in Central Europe and once dominated Western Europe (around 400BC).
- people migrated across to the British Isles over 2000 years ago
- when the Germanic speaking Anglo Saxons arrived, the Celtic speakers were pushed into
- One group of Celts moved back to France. Their language became **Breton**
- Other Celtic languages have become extinct. These include **Cornish** (Cornwall in England), **Gaulish** (France), **Cumbrian** (Wales), **Manx** (Isle of Man), **Pictish** (Scotland) and **Galatian** (Anatolia)
- Welsh: word order **Verb-Subject-Object**

Irish Gaelic

Sláinte: cheers

Go raibh maith agat: Thank you

Seán is ainm dom: My name is Seán

Backgrounds - IE Langs.: *Germanic*

- **Proto-Germanic / Germanic**
- influence of early Christian missionaries → Celtic and Germanic languages use the Latin Alphabet
- Branches: **North** (Danish, Norwegian), **East** (Gothic, Vandalic), **West** (English, Frisian, Dutch, German)
- **Icelandic** is the least changed of the Germanic Languages, **Flemish** and **Afrikaans** are varieties of Dutch while **Yiddish** is a variety of German
- German has a system of four **cases** and three **genders** for its nouns
- English has lost gender and case

Map of Languages in Europe

Backgrounds: Major Changes from IE Germanic

- **Germanic** languages are distinguished for:
 1. Gmc → wide word stock with no cognates in other IE langs.: broad, drive, hold, found, meat
 2. IE tense and aspect in verbs were lost except present / past. No future tenses in Gmc langs.
 3. All Gmc langs. → past tense with a dental suffix = -t / -d
 - All Gmc verbs → 2 classes of verbs (+/+ dental suf.)
 - Jacob Grimm called them regular / irregular
 - Historically, buy, drink are weak but have vowel gradation
 4. All Gmc langs. → 2 types of declensions for adj.:
 - the weak → determiner + adj. + noun
 - the strong → ∅ + adj. + noun

Backgrounds: Major Changes from IE Germanic

5. Free accentual system → tendency to stress on the 1st syllable (except with prefixes)
6. IE vowels changed → Gmc
 - IE o → Gmc a Lat. octo → Gothic ahtau
 - IE ā → Gmc ō Lat. māter → OE mōdor
7. First Sound Shift

Backgrounds: GRIMM'S LAW

1. IE **bh** → **β** → **b** (initial position)
 dh → **δ** → **d**
 gh → **γ** → **g**

IE

bh – bhrater

Dh – dhwer

Gh – ghosti

Gmc

b- brother

d – door

g – guest

Latin

f frater

f- foris

h- hosti

Backgrounds: GRIMM's LAW

2. When not preceded by s:

IE	→	Gmc
p	→	f
t	→	θ
k	→	χ (h)

IE	Gmc	Latin
p – pisk	f – fish	p – piscis
t – treyes	θ – three	t – tres
k – kerd	h – heart	c – cord

Backgrounds: GRIMM's LAW

3. IE b → p
 d → t
 g → k

IE

d – dwo

g – genu

Gmc

t – two

k – knee

Latin

d – duo

g – genu

Backgrounds: **VERNER'S LAW**

- Grimm's Law had many exceptions
- Karl Verner (1885) explained that:

f	→	β
θ	→	ð
χ	→	γ
s	→	z

Except when the sound:

- was the 1st sound in a word**
- was next to a voiceless sound**
- had the IE stress on the preceding syllable**

Ex.:	Grimm		Verner
	IE t → Gmc θ	→	Icelandic ð
	pater		faðir
	faθer		

Old English

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Pre-Old English

- Celts → group of peoples loosely tied by similar language, religion, and cultural expression
- lived in central and western Europe from 1000 BC (3000 years ago)
- not centrally governed → divided into **clans**
- lived in huts of arched timber and roofs of thatch
- Warriors and farmers, society based on glories of battle and plunder.
- brought iron working to England.
- Women were technically equal to men, owned property, and could choose their own husbands

Pre-Old English

- **Religion:** held many of their religious ceremonies in woodland groves and near sacred water, such as wells and springs
- human sacrifice as part of Celtic religion
- **Druids:** sort of super-class of priests, political advisors, teachers, healers, and arbitrators, they acted as ambassadors in time of war, they composed verse and upheld the law

Pre-Old English

- **Language:** written **Celtic** language, but it developed well into Christian times
- There was a unifying language spoken by the Celts, old Celtic
- Celtic languages spoken in Great Britain, Ireland, and Brittany → two groups:
 - **Q-Celtic**, or **Goedelic**, spoken in Ireland, the Isle of Man, and western Scotland,
 - **P-Celtic**, or **Brythonic**, which forms the basis of modern Welsh, Cornish, and Breton

Pre-Old English

• The Romans

- In 55 B.C Julius Caesar, general of the Roman armies invaded Britain
 - *The Celts in Gaul helped by Celts in southern England.
- Caesar's invasion was successful but inconclusive
- He landed in Kent in summer & went back home and next summer returned
- No permanent Roman occupation, several attempts during the following century
- contacts between the Roman Empire and Celtic England grew: Trade

The Romans

Pre-Old English

- In 43 A.D. **Claudius** → Emperor of Rome, decided to invade Britain
- Vespasian's 2nd Legion marched through Sussex and Hampshire, the lands of the Atrebates
- 1st plan → limit conquest to south of modern England → a border was established by 47 A.D. along **Fosse Way** (the great Roman road running from Exeter to Lincoln)
- But Celtic leader Caratacus, (fled to Wales) attacked Romans with help of Silures in SE and Ordovices in N
- Caratacus defeated in 51 A.D.
- Colchester → 1st capital of the Roman province
- Later moved it to a small settlement by the Thames River → **Londinium**

Pre-Old English

- **The Romans**
- 122 A.D. → Emperor Hadrian decided that the Empire needed securing, not expanding → build a wall across the northern frontier, it took 6 years to complete
- Romans set up administrative centres according to traditional tribal territories
- they encouraged the growth of towns → urban life
- They encourage commercial activity
 - *imported Roman wine, jewellery, and pottery. In return they exported cattle, grain, lead, iron, tin*

Pre-Old English

The Romans

- Every town had public baths, open to both sexes, though at different times of day, and served as a combination health club, healing spa, and meeting place
- Promoted theatre and amphitheatre
- Built several Roman roads
- Constructed villas → country estates of the Romanised British elite

**The Ermine
Street Guard,
Colchester**

Pre-Old English

- Some British Towns come from the **Romans**:
 - *caster* < chester (campamento):
Manchester, Colchester, Silchester, Winchester
 - *-ton*: Casteton, Chesterton,
 - *Bath*
 - Portsmouth
 - Fosham
- **Celtic** Origin placenames:
 - Kent, Devon, Avon, Dover, London ...

Pre-Old English

King Arthur?

- End of 3rd c A.D. → 1st Germanic attacks
- 409 Romans left Britain definitely to defend Rome
- Britons were left alone against the Germanic tribes
- King Arthur → ‘British hero’
- Was King Arthur real?
 - **MYTH**: Not as Thomas Mallory depicted him
 - **MYTH**: no knights in shining armour searching for the Holy Grail in Arthur's company
 - **MYTH**: no Round Table or Sword in the stone
 - **REAL**: a very brave warrior, maybe named Arthur, leading the remnants of romanised British resistance against the Germanic invaders

Pre-Old English

King Arthur?

- Arthur was Welsh, Celtic, or Breton
- fought the Saxons in the north, in the south, or in Wales, around the year 450, or 500, or 525
- The real Arthur may have been a man named Ambrosius Aurelianus, or perhaps his war leader, who defeated the Saxons in a major battle we know as Mount Badon
- The rest of the story is **Romantic fiction**

Historical Introduction

- **Who were the Germanic tribes?**
- **Where did they come from?**
- **Why did they invade England? And when?**
- **What linguistic consequences did it have?**

Old English

Germanic Invasions in Europe

Anglo-Saxon Civilization

- Germanic people > tribes
- Roman towns burnt
- In time, several kingdoms appeared
- Anglo-Saxon Heptarchy, not permanent
- Leadership:
 - 7th Northumbria
 - 8th Mercia
 - 9th Wessex

Old English

- **Anglo-Saxon Invasions**
 - 449 Jutes, Angles, Saxons → England
 - ‘The Saxon Shore’ under Roman Protection
 - Picts and Scots in the North
 - Vortigern → Celtic leader
 - Jutes → Kent
 - Saxons → Sussex (477) & Wessex (495)
 - Angles → East Coast → Northumbria (547)
 - Bede’s *Ecclesiastical History of the English People* (731)

Old English

- Celts → Cornwall, Wales
- Anglo-Saxon Heptarchy:
 - **Kent**
 - Culture + wealth (6th)
 - King ethelbert → Christianity
 - **Northumbria**
 - Literature + learning (7th)
 - Lindisfarne, Wearmouth, Jarrow
 - **Mercia** (8th)
 - **Wessex** (9th)
 - Egbert (803-839) → 830, overlordship
 - Alfred the Great (871-889) → ‘Rex Anglorum’

Old English

The Anglo-Saxon Heptarchy

Old English

- **Alfred the Great**

- His entire reign was spent in a religious war with the Danes
- Alfred the Great, against Vikings → Ashdown (871), Wareham and Exeter (875), Treaty of Wedmore (878) .
- Alfred made Guthrum convert to Christianity

Old English

• Alfred the Great

- Brought many Latin scholars from the continent to teach at his institutions: Archbishop Plegmund and Bishop Werfrith (Mercia), Grimbold, John Scotus, Asser, etc
- He founded monasteries: Shaftesbury, Athelney
- Took the first steps for what was later called the '**Benedictine Reform**' (end of 10th c)
- **Winchester** → cultural capital of England
- Old English vs Old Norse
- Old English vs. Latin
 - He learnt Latin in his late 30s!!!
- translated several Latin works:
 - Pope Gregory the Great's *Pastoral Care*
 - Boethius's *Consolation of Philosophy*
 - St. Augustine's *Soliloquies*
 - Orosius' *History of the World*
 - Bede's *Eccliastical History*
- commanded other works: the *Anglo-Saxon Chronicle* ...

Anglo-Saxon Civilization

- Society divided into:
 - æðelings
 - eorls
 - ðegns
 - ceorls (geneatas, kotsetla, gebur)
 - ðeow
- Justice based on *weregild*
- 597, St, Augustine sent to convert the heathen people
- By 700 all Anglo-Saxon England was Christian

Old English Vocabulary

- **Germanic vocabulary**
 - *cild* = child *-scip* = ship *-dæg* = day
- **Some words had different meaning:**
 - *dream* = joy *-winnan* = fight *-sellan* = give
- **Word formation:**
 - **compounding:** *æftergengness* = succession
 - **self-explaining compounds:** *dægred* < *dæg*+*red* = dawn
 - **derivation:** *onwæcnan* = awake, *synnfull* = sinful
 - **borrowing:**
 - Celtic: *Kent*, *Thames*, *Avon*, *Brae* (hill), *dunn* (grey) ...
 - Latin: *altar*, *daemon*, *prior*, *clericus*, *grammatica* ...
 - Scandinavian: *they*, *sky*, *skill*, *sister*, *egg*, *kid* ...
 - Kennings: *hronr~d* (whale+road = sea), *beadol'oma* (battle+light = sword)

Old English

• Vocabulary:

- Most OE words lost → After Norman Conquest (1066) many OE words → replaced by French words
- OE words that survive are widely used: man, child, house, eat, do, run, go ...
- Some OE words were identical to ModE: god, hand, land ...

Others changed meaning:

- *Bread* = *bit, piece* *NOT* *bread*
 - *Dream* = *joy* *NOT* *dream, visio in sleep*
 - *Hlaf* = *bread* *NOT* *loaf*
 - *Sellan* = *give* *NOT* *sell*
- Some OE words have survived only in ModE expressions:
guma = bridegroom
 - Many OE words did not survive: blican, leax ...
 - OE had grammatical gender <-> ‘natural gender’
 - IE had 3 genders that survive only in modern Icelandic and German: masc, fem., neuter

Old English

- Place names ending in in:

	OE	Example
– <i>Ton</i>	<i>tun</i> = fence	<i>Brompton</i>
– <i>Ham</i>	<i>hamm</i> = village	<i>Chatham</i>
– <i>Wick/which</i>	<i>wic</i> = dwelling	<i>Sandwich</i>
– <i>Worth</i>	<i>worth</i> = homestead	<i>Mereworth</i>
– <i>Ness</i>	<i>næs</i> = headland	<i>Sheerness</i>
– <i>Bridge</i>	<i>brycg</i> = bridge	<i>Tonbridge</i>
– <i>Burton /bury</i>	<i>burh</i> = fort	<i>Canterbury</i>

- Saxons → Britons = ‘**wealas**’ = foreigners → Wales

- Days of week:

– Monandæg → moon	Tiwesdæg → god Tiw
– Wodnesdæg → god Woden	Ʒunresdæg → god Ʒunor
– Frigedæg → goddess Friga	Sæaternesdæg → god Saturn
– Sunnadæg → sun	

- Some Anglo-Saxon words → changed spelling: *æfter*, *beforan*, *behindan*, *eall*, *æg*, *uppan*, *mete*, *scyrte*

Old English

- **Introduction of Christianity:**

- 597 → Pope Gregory I → missionaries to ‘Angli’
 - St. Augustine – Kent → king Ethelbert baptized
- 601 → **Augustine**, 1st archbishop of Canterbury, established Church in England
- Irish missionaries → monasteries (Lindisfarne, etc) in Northumbria → St. Patrick
- 7th c spread of new faith
- **Consequences** of Christian spread:
 - Great influx of Latin words into English
 - Building of churches, monasteries (schools)

Old English

LATIN INFLUENCE on OE

- Contact with Latin (Roman = conquerors) → higher civilization. Types of contact

a) commercial & military b) religious & intellectual

- **3 PERIODS:**

- **1st PERIOD (Continental)**

- 1st contacts continent
 - Several million Germans lived within Roman Empire (slaves, mercenaries, etc)
 - 1st Latin words → trade & war:

WAR

camp (Battle)

weall (wall)

Stræt (street)

TRADE

ceap (cheap)

pund (pound)

win (wine)

DOMESTIC

mese (table)

cycene (kitchen)

disc (dish)

FOOD

ciese (cheese)

butere (butter)

yne (onion)

Old English

2nd PERIOD (Christianizing per. 6th-10th c)

- 597 → introduction of Christianity
- Official religion and unofficial practice was contradictory:

Germanic

Physical courage

Independence

Loyalty to one's leader

Revenge

Fame and joy

Latin

meeknes and humility

submissiveness

loyalty to God

forgive

suffering and patience

- Building of churches and monstaries
- Words adopted:

Religious

abbot, alter

anthem, ark

canon, cleric

pope, nun, mass

shrine, priest, psalm ...

Domestic

cap, silk,

purple

School

school, master,

grammatic,

verse, notary

Others

anchor

elephant

circl ...

Old English

- **3rd PERIOD: The Benedictine Reform**

- 9th & 10th c → Viking raids, destroyed monasteries, etc
- Alfred the Great started → **Benedictine Reform** (end of 10th c):
 - Alfred's time → Dunstan (Archbishop of Cant.)
 - Edgar's time → Athelwold (bishop Winchester) & Oswald (archbishop York)
- Reformed and created monastic schools
- **Latin words** adopted:
 - Religious: *antichrist, canticle, cell, cloister, collect, demon, idol, prophet ...*
 - Others: *accent, decline, paper, title, etc*

Old English

- After Alfred the Great's death several weak leaders (son Edgar and grandson Aethelstan)
- **Ethelred the Unready** (original term → 'no council'), came to the throne at the age of ten when his mother had his half-brother Edward murdered
- He was reputed as a bad leader, a chronicler called the king "eager and admirably fitted for sleeping"
- In the 990s several **Viking raids**

Ethelred
The 'Unready'

Old English

The Vikings

Old English

Old English

Invasions in the IXth-Xth Century

Old English

Old English

The Vikings in Spain

Old English

1st Viking Invasion

- End of 8th c vikings raided Lindisfarne and Jarrow (793)
- **865** → **Ivar the Boneless** and brother Halfdan landed in East Anglia
- **870** → attacked Wessex (Ethelred & Alfred)
- Swein forced submissions in the north and finally defeated Ethelred (fled to Normandy)

Old English

• 1st Viking Invasion

- 878 → Alfred won battle at Eddington over Guthrum (Danish king of East Anglia)

- Treaty of Wedmore → **Danelaw**

Old English

2nd Viking Invasion

- End of **10th** c warriors led by Olaf Tryggvason and Svein Forkbeard invaded England
- ‘*The Battle of Maldon*’, Vikings won over Saxons
- 1016 Ethelred + son Edmund Ironside → **Cnut** (Svein Forkbeard’s son) ruled England
- Cnut married Ethelred’s widow, Emma of Normandy
- **1042** Line of Aldred the Great restored → **Edward the Confessor**

Old English

•Society:

- Vikings lived in large family groups
- Men had to provide food to the family and women were responsible for cooking and farm animals
- Girls were married at the age of 12 –15 (agreed between families), but women could divorce
- Slaves had no legal rights except as property of the owner

•LAW

- The 'ting' was the Viking word for a legislative assembly and a court
- A jury of 12, two times twelve or three times twelve, depending on the importance of the case, decided the question of guilt
- Holmgang (A duel) was a common way of solving disputes
- Swords and shields were favourite weapons
- Walking 12 paces on red-hot irons could prove innocence if after 3 days the feet were inspected and the wounds were found clean

•Religion:

- They knew the gods lived in Asgard
- Sacrificed animals (blota) to the gods
- Old Norse Mythology → Sagas (= Tolkien, Wagner ...)
- Different gods and creatures (elves, etc)

Old English

- After **Cnut** died in 1035 → dynastic squabbles
- Edward, surviving son of Ethelred, was called back from exile in Normandy to rule
- called "**Edward** the Confessor" for his religious bent, had lived in Normandy for 25 years
- founder of Westminster Abbey
- Edward approached old age without a son to succeed him → name an heir
- two chief candidates:
 - 1. **Harold** Godwinson, a prominent earl
 - 2. **William**, Duke of Normandy
- Edward named Harold as his heir

**Edward
the Confessor**

Old English

- **Edward** died on January 5 1066
- On the same day **Harold** was crowned king of England
- Duke **William** amassed an invasion fleet
- When king Harold was ready to fight in the South, news came from the North, an invasion by Harald Hardrada, King of Norway
- Harold marched north with his own personal army and defeated the Norwegians at Stamford Bridge
- William attacked in the South, near Hastings, Harold marched back with his tired troops
→ **The Battle of Hastings (1066)**
- The Norman knights defeated the English
- With the defeat of Harold the Dark Ages come officially to an end → **Middle English Period**

Harold

William

Old English

- **Vikings' Language** → Old Norse, several Scandinavian variations (Old Icelandic, etc)
- OE and ON → Germanic langs.
- Common words:

<i>OE</i>	<i>ON</i>	<i>North England</i>
<i>cild</i>	<i>barn</i>	<i>bairn</i>
- English words of **Norse origin**: *take, call, die, flat, tight, kid, steaj, anger, awe, wand, wrong, freckle.*
- **Place names**:
 - York → Eorforwic = ‘wild boar settlement’
 - Beck → bekkkr = brook ex.: Birbeck
 - Fell → fell = hill ex.: Hampsfell
- **Personal names**:
 - From Anglo-Saxons: Edgar, Agatha, Edith ...
 - From Vikings: Erik, Freda, Karl, Neil ...
- **Surnames**:
 - Anglo-Saxons: place of origin / job ex.: Edward (Black)Smith
 - Vikings: father's or mother's name: Harald Erikson (son or Erik) or nicknames: the wise, boneless, forkbeard ...

Old English

• Viking influence on English language:

- Racial and linguistic kinship
- intermarriage
- 1,400 Norse place names in England
- Many words in common: *man, can, wife, folk, house, will, can, come, hear, see, think, ride, etc*
- Vikings words replaced some Saxon words: sister (ON systir)
- Norse place name endings:
 - **By** (farm or town)
Grimsby, Derby
 - **thwaite** (isolated land)
Applethwaite
 - **Thorpe** (village)
Althorp, Linthorp
 - **toft** (piece of ground)
Brimtoft, Langtoft

Old English alphabet: The Runes

- OE -> **runic** alphabet
- Runes -> North. Europe
- 4,000 inscriptions, 3rd c AD aprox.
- origin unknown
- meaning: whisper, secret, mystery ...
- each letter = name
- 1st 6 letters = **futhark**
- several runic alphabets (Old Norse, Old Swedish, Old High German, Old English, etc)

 w							
 s							
 o							

Old English alphabet: futhorc

- Old English: included other letters for OE sounds
- 3 I letters: Norhtumbrian version (9th c.)
- found in weapons, monuments, jewellery, etc

feoh (cattle, weath)	ur (aurochs)	þorn (thorn)	ōs (god)	rād (journey/riding)	cen (torch)	giefu (gift)	wyn (joy)
f	u	þ	o	r	c	g[]	ƿ
hægl (hail)	nied (necessity/trouble)	is (ice)	gear (iron)	ēoh (yew)	peor (?)	eolh (sedge?)	sigel (sun)
h	n	i	j	3	ƿ	x	s
tiw/tir (Tiw - a god)	beorc (birch)	eoh (horse)	man (man)	lagu (water/sea)	lng (a god)	eþel (land/estate)	dæg (day)
t	b	e	m	l	ng	ce	d

Old English dialects

- **Norhtumbrian**
- **Mercian**
- **West-Saxon / kentish**

• *Reasons:*

- use of diphthongs instead of vowels in Wessex: *giet* <> *get*
- use of o instead of a before m, n & ng in Mercian & Northumbrian: *mon* <> *man*

Old English

- Old English dialects:
 - Mercian + Northumbrian → Anglian speech
 - Scant records left of Anglian and Kentish dialects
 - Standard ModE → Mercian (London)
 - Old English → West Saxon English
 - Winchester → capital of Wessex, cultural center
 - OE dictionaries based on Wessex dialect:
 - Exceptions: eald (Wessex) <> ald (Angliand) = old
 - Classical Old English period → Aelfric's period (1,000 year approx.)
 - West Saxon dialect, **2 periods**:
 - Early West Saxon → Alfred's time (9th c)
 - Late West Saxon → Aelfric's time (10th c), Benedictine reform

PADRENUESTRO

Old English dialects

1. Old English (Lindisfarne, 950), Northumbrian dialect:

Fader ures þu **arþ** þu bist in **heofnum** in heofnas, sic
gehaldað noma þin **to-cymer rice þin**; sie willo þin swæ is in
heofne ond in eorðo: hlaf uresne ofer wistlic sel us
todæg ond forgef us scylda usra vœ forgef on scyldgum
usum; ond ne inlæd usih in costunge, ah gefrig usih
from yfele.

2. Old English (Rusthworth, 960-980), Mercian dialect:

Fæder ure þu þe in **heofonum** **earð** beo gehalgod þin
norna; **cume to þin rice**; weorðe þin willa swa swa on
heofone swilce on eorpe; hlaf uresne instondenlice sel us to
dæge; ond forlet us ure scyldes swa swa we ec forleten
þæm þe scyldigat wið us; ond ne gelætet us gelæde in costungæ,
ah gelese us of yfele.

3. Old English (Winchester, around 1000), Wessex dialect

Fæder ure þu þe **earþ** on **heofonum** si þin nama gehald
to-becume þin rice, gewurpe þin willa on eorða swa swa on heofonum
urne gedaghwamlican hlaf syle us to dæg; and forgyf us ure gylt
swa swa we forgyfað urum gyltendum; and ne gelæd þu us
on costunge, ac alys us of yfele, soþlice.

4. Old English (Exeter Book, end of the 10th century), literary Wessex dialect:

(Hali)g Fæder, þu þe on heofonum **earðast**,
geweorðað wuldres dreame. Sy þinum weorcum halgað
noma nifra bearnum; þu earþ nergend wera.
Cyme þin rice wide ond þin rædfæst willa
aræred under rodores hrofe, eac þan on rumre foldan;
syle us to dæge donfæstne blæd,
hlaf uresne, helpend wera,
þone singalan, soðfæst meotod;
No læt usic costunga enyssan to swiðe,
ac þu us freedom gief, folca waldend,
from ylla gehwam, a to widan feore.

OE Phonology: vowels & diphthongs

SPELLING SOUND		SPELLING SOUND		SPELLING SOUND	
a	[a]	i	[i]	y	[ū]
ā	[ā]	ī	[ī]	y:	[ū̄]
æ	[æ]	o	[ɔ]	ea	[æə]
ǣ	[ǣ]	ō	[ō]	ēa	[ǣə]
e	[ɛ]	u	[u]	eo	[ɛə]
ē	[ē]	ū	[ū]	ēo	[ēə]

		Front Unrounded	Front Rounded	Back or Central
HIGH	<i>Long</i>	ī	ū	ū
	<i>short</i>	i	ü	u
MED	<i>Long</i>	ē	DIPHTHONGS	
	<i>short</i>	ɛ	ēə	ɔ
LOW	<i>Long</i>	ǣ	ǣə	ā
	<i>short</i>	æ	æə	a

OE vowels & diphthongs

OLD ENGLISH			MODERN ENGLISH		
vowel	(1) phonetic symbol	key words	Key words	(2) phonetic symbol	(3) typical spelling
a	[a]	habban batt sadol lamb	have but saddle lamb	[æ]	a
ā	[ā]	ham gad tacen pal	home goad token pole	[o]	o
æ	[æ]	þæt pæt bæc mæst	that path back mast	[æ]	a
ǣ	[ǣ]	dǣl nǣdl hǣlan mǣne	deal needle heal mean	[i]	e
e	[ɛ]	settan weddian rest denn	set wed rest den	[ɛ]	e
ē	[ē]	fēdan cēne grēne mētan	feed keen green meet	[i]	e
i	[i]	sittan timber mist rima	sit timber mist rim	[i]	[i]
ī	[ī]	rīdan tīma līf bī	ride time life by	[ai]	i
o	o	moððe pott oft botm	moth pot of(ten) bottom	[a]	o

OLD ENGLISH			MODERN ENGLISH		
vowel	(1) phonetic symbol	key words	key words	(2) phonetic symbol	(3) typical spelling
ō	[ō]	fōða gōd nōn brōm	food good noon broom	[ʊ]	oo
u	[u]	sundor wundor þus pullian	sunder wonder thus pull	[ə]	u
ū	[ū]	mūs nū dūne ūt	mouse now down out	[aʊ]	ou
y	[y]	fyllan pytt mynster þynne	fill pit minster thin	[i]	i
y:	[y]	mȳst fȳr hȳdan hwȳ	mice fire minister thin	[aɪ]	i
ea	[æ]	ċeaf sleac nearu fealu	chaff slack narrow fallow	[æ]	a
ēa	[ǣ]	bēatan ēast lēaf stēap	beat east leaf steep	[i]	ea
eo	[ɛ]	ġeolu heofon eolh seofon	yellow heaven elk seven	[ɛ]	e
ēo	[ē]	crēopan dēop flēon bēo	creep deep flee bee	[i]	e

Old English Phonology: consonants

Spelling	Sound	Spelling	Sound	Spelling	Sound
b	[b]	h	[h], [x], [ç] ²	s	[s], [z]
c,k	[k]	l	[l]	t	[t]
c ³	[č]	m	[m]	þ, ð	[θ], [ð]
d	[d]	n	[n], [ŋ]	w	[w]
f	[f], [v]	p	[p]	sc	[š]
g	[g], [ɣ] ²	r	[r]	cg	[ǰ]
g ³	[y]				

²To pronounce [x] and [ç] you may find one or more of the following techniques helpful: (1) Start to make the sound [k], but stop before the back of the tongue actually touches the roof of the mouth, and breathe out strongly; or make a [k] with light contact between the tongue and the roof of the mouth, and with the tongue still in that position, breathe out strongly, or (2) make an [š] sound, and while you are making it, force your tongue as far back in the mouth as it will go, the result being [x]; or (3) make the [hj] sound as in *hew* forcefully so that the [h] and [j] blend into a single sound, which will be [ç]. Palatal [ç] and velar [x] differ from each other much as do the [k] sounds of *keen* and *corn*. Children sometimes use repeated [x]'s.

Old English Phonology: consonants

Consonants	same as ModE., but	with a few	exceptions
<i>Spelling</i>	<i>phonetic environment</i>	<i>pronunciation</i>	<i>example</i>
c	-before back vowels a, o, u, y -before i -before e, æ	/k/ /t ¹⁰ /k/ or /t ¹⁰	<i>cuman</i> <i>cild</i> <i>cen, spræce</i>
f	-in voiceless environment -in voiced environment	/f/ /v/	<i>fram</i> <i>scefing</i>
g	-before a, o, u, y -before i -before e, æ	/g/ /j/ /g/ or /g/	<i>God</i> <i>gif</i> <i>gelæred</i>
s	-in voiceless environment -in voices environment	/s/ [z]	<i>sum</i> <i>wisdom</i>
þ, ð	-in voiceless environment -in voiced environment	/θ/ /ð/	<i>þrim</i> <i>suþan</i>
cg	in all positions	/d [⊙]	<i>secgan</i>
sc	-before and after back vowels -in all the other positions	/sk/ /t ¹⁰	<i>tuscas</i> <i>scip</i>

OE Phonology: pronunciation

- Prefix **ge-**: always unaccented
 - no voicing: (ex. *gefleogan*)
- Prepositional prefixes (*for*, *ofer*, etc) can be accented: *fórwyrd* or unaccented *forwíernan*
- compound words may have 2nd stress

Domesday

Beowulf

OE Phonology: Changes

- Umlaut / vowel mutation / metaphony
 - anticipatory vowel assimilation occurring in the Gmnc langs.
 - Ex.: **i-mutation**: *manniz > men, *fçtiz > feet ...
 - *How do you do? <> How are you doing?*
- Ablaut / vowel gradation / apophony
 - variation of a root for grammatical purposes ex. *sing/sang/sung*
 - *Strong verbs* ex. *gelimpan / gelamp / gelumpon*
 - *weak verbs* (dental suffix -ode, -ede, -de) ex. *clipian / clipode*
- Other changes: *syncope, contraction, alternation æ/a, diphthongisation before velarised consonants, diphthongisation after palatal consonants ...*

Old English

NOUNS

- In OE: nouns, adjectives, most pronouns were inflected & verbs conjugated
- NOUNS = a stem + case ending

- Nouns may change case and number depending on syntax but never change gender
- Inflections reduced through time by analogisation and weakening of unstressed syllables
- In ModE only plural morph – s and some irregular plural forms survive: men, feet, oxen, mice, etc
- Originally in OE → 10 noun classes. By 9th c reduced to 3 main classes
- Noun Inflections divided (depending on IE root) into:
 - vocalic (strong)*
 - consonantal (weak)*

Old English

OE nouns:

– 4 cases:

- NOMINATIVE → subject
- ACCUSATIVE → object
- GENITIVE → possessive
- DATIVE → indirect object, place, time, etc

– Strong declension

	<i>Sing.</i>	<i>Plural</i>
N.	<i>st~n</i>	<i>st~nas</i>
A.	<i>st~n</i>	<i>st~nas</i>
G.	<i>st~nes</i>	<i>st~na</i>
D.	<i>st~ne</i>	<i>st~num</i>

Weak declension

	<i>Sing.</i>	<i>Plural</i>
	<i>nama</i>	<i>naman</i>
	<i>naman</i>	<i>naman</i>
	<i>naman</i>	<i>namen</i>
	<i>naman</i>	<i>nam(en)un</i>

– Modern survivals of case + number:

- Genitive plural ending ‘-a-’ → ME ‘-e’
ex *mila* → *mile* in *sixty-mile drive*
- Dative plural ending –um ex.: *whilom* (< *hwilum*), *seldom*

Old English

- OE Nouns, **exceptions**:

- 1. *Masculine nouns*:

- Two-syllabled nouns whose 1st syllable is long and 2nd is short → lose the vowel of the 2nd syllable in inflected forms through **SYNCOPE**:

dryhten / dryhten / dryht(e)nes / dryht(e)ne (lord)

- In one-syllable nouns with <-æ> in the sing. alternates with <-a> in the plural:

SING. *dæg / dæg / dæges / dæge* (day)

PLURAL *dagas / dagas / dagum / daga*

- 2. *Neuter nouns*:

- Nouns whose stems end in <-h> lose it in inflected forms:

SING. *feorh / feorh / feores / feore* (life)

PLURAL *feorh / feorh / feora / feorum*

- Nouns which end in <-e> keep it in the singular but lose it in the plural:

SING. *rŷce / rŷce / rŷces / rŷce* (kindom)

PLURAL *rŷc(i)u / rŷc(i)u / rŷc(i)um / rŷc(e)a*

Old English

- OE **ADJECTIVES:**

- 2 declensions: **strong** and **weak**:

- *Strong* if not preceded by determiner (article, demonstrative):

- ex.: *gŕd man* = *good man*

- *Weak* if followed by determiner

- ex.: *se gŕda man* = *the/this good man*

- Grades:

- *Comparative* : suffix **–ra** *heard* → *heard**ra*** (harder)

- *Superlative* : suffix **–ost** *heard* → *heard**ost*** (hardest)

- Irregular forms:

- gŕd / betra / betst*

- micel / m~ra / mæst*

- OE **ADVERBS:**

- Adjectives + suffix **–e**

- Ex. *wrađ* (=angry)

- wrađe* (=angrily)

- Suffix **–lice** = **-ly**

- Ex.: *huxlice sođlice* ...

Old English

• OE PRONOUNS

- OE Pronouns had 7 diff. functions: *demonstrative, personal, possessive, reflexive, relative, interrogative, indefinite.*
- **Demonstrative:**
 - S', s'ō, Þæt / Þ's, Þ'os, Þis → also definite articles
 - Ex *Þæt word = the word / this word*
- **Personal Pronouns:** singular, plural, dual
 - Dual: only in 1st and 2nd persons
 - Wit = we two - git = you two
- **Possessive:** genitive case of plural pronouns
 - -mʒn, Þʒn, his / hire / his → sing
 - -āre, 'ower, hira → plural
- **Reflexive:** dative or accus. case of personal pronouns
- **Relative:** most frequent is invariable particle Þe = that
- **Interrogative:** hwæðer (which of two), hwelc (which of many)

Old English

• OE VERBS:

- 2 verb tenses: Present & Past
- Indicative, Subjunctive Moods
- 2 numbers and 3 persons

– STRONG VERBS:

- Modified root vowel
- Less numerous than weak (300 approx.)
- Regular sequence in vowel changes:
 - OE Past Tense:
 - » 1st + 3rd person sing → one vowel
 - » 2nd + all Plurals → another vowel
- 4 forms, ex. *dr̥ʃfan* (*drive*)

Infinitive

dr̥ʃfan

Pret. Sing.

dr̥f

Pret. Pl.

drif(on)

Past Part.

(ge)drifen

Old English

- **Old English Literature**

- Famous **monasteries** → centers of learning (Lindisfarne, Jarrow, etc)
- Several famous scholars: *Bede*, *Alcuin*, etc
- Old English poetry was meant to be declaimed aloud before an audience, the poet, or **Scop**, being both a creative and a performing artist
- Poetry accompanied by **harp**, poet entertained the guests of his patron with tales of past deeds and battles
- Characteristics:
 - *Alliteration*
 - *Metaphors* (**kennings**) ex.: sea = whale's way', 'gannet's bath', 'swan's riding'
- 2 sorts of literature
 - **PAGAN**
 - **CHRISTIAN**

Old English

PAGAN LITERATURE:

– BEOWULF:

- written about **1000 A.D** by two scribes in late West Saxon
- dates ranging from the sixth century to the early eleventh century have been proposed for the composition of *Beowulf*
- elaborated upon for centuries by **minstrels** who **recited** the heroic exploits of King of the Geats, whose kingdom was what is now Southern Sweden
- **Beowulf** → strong and brave. He rescued Hrothgar, King of Denmark, from the monster, Grendel, and later saved his own kingdom from the fiery **dragon** which dealt Beowulf a mortal blow.

Old English

PAGAN LITERATURE:

– BEOWULF:

- traditional heroic poem in **alliterative** verse
 - A line of verse is divided into two half-lines → caesura
 - Each half-line has two strongly stressed words, or "lifts,"
 - At least two, usually three, of the lifts in a whole line must alliterate with each other.
- lack of any Scandinavian loan words, suggests a pre-Viking date (<835)
- loss of intervocalic *h*
- occasional lack of smoothing (an Anglian phenomenon in which diphthongs (*ea*, *eo*, *io*) were monophthongised to *æ*, *e*, *i*, respectively, before the back consonants (*c* [k], *g* [g], *h*[x])),

GRENDL

Old English

• **BEDE:**

- **Bede**, or *Baeda* in Old English (it means "priest" in Old Saxon), was born about 672 or 673 A.D. in Northumbria
- 7 years old → monastery at Wearmouth → **Benedictine Rule**
- very well educated. He learned calligraphy in the scriptorium, grammar, computus, music, and something of the natural science
- Produced 2 famous works:
 - *History of the Abbots of Wearmouth and Jarrow*
 - *The Ecclesiastical History of the English People*

Old English

PAGAN LITERATURE:

– Poetry of Native Tradition:

- Widsith
- Deor
- The Wanderer

– War Poems:

- **The Battle of Brunanburh:**

- date (937 A.D.) leaders: Aethelstan and Eadmund leading the English; Constantine and Anlaf leading the Picts and Vikings

- **The Battle of Maldon**

- describes a battle against the Dane in 991, the Saxon won over the Vikings

Old English

CHRISTIAN LITERATURE:

– Poetry:

• Caedmon

- Author of Biblical Poems in Anglo-Saxon
- Birthdate (??) - died between 670 and 680
- Caedmonian poems, found in a unique tenth-century manuscript
- manuscript consists of poems on *Genesis*, *Exodus*, *Daniel*, and a group of poems in a different hand, now called collectively "Christ and Satan"

• Cynewulf:

- Not clear who he was (Bishop of Lindisfarne?)
- Many poems, but he is clearly the author of 4:
 - » *The Fates of the Apostles*
 - » *Christ*
 - » *Judith*
 - » *Phoenix*

CAEDMON'S HYMN OF CREATION

Old English

CHRISTIAN LITERATURE:

– Prose:

– King Alfred's translations:

- *Pastoral care*
- *Ecclesiastical History*
- *Orosius' World History*
- *Boethius' Consolation of Philosophy*
- *The Anglo-Saxon Chronicle*

65
Land. 7 hit mid his gearweorde swa swiðe smeode. 7 næf an hid lan-
des innan engla lande. 7 þe nyste hwa heo hæfde. odde hwæt
heo wære. 7 7yððan on his geƿur ge lætt. Ðryceland him
wære on geƿalde. 7 he wære inne cæsteles geƿolte. 7 þer man
cym mid ealle geƿalde. Ðwilec eac scotland he hi under þeod-
de. 7 on his mycele sciens þe. Noƿmandige 7 land wære hit
ge cýnde. 7 ofer þone eorðas þe man is 7 hæten he ƿurde.
7 þer he moƿte þa 57 tpa gear libban. he hæfde ƿilande
mid his gearweorde geƿunon. 7 ƿið utan alcon ƿæron. Ði
todlice on his tamen hæfdon men mycel 7 sƿiðe ma-
nges tænan. Cætelas he lec ƿƿeacan. 7 earms men sƿiðe
spencan. Ðe cýng wære swa sƿiðe fæst. 7 þena of hit un-
der þeodan man. manges maðes goldes. 7 ma hundred
ƿunda seolƿes. Ðer he nā be ƿilte. 7 mid mycelan un-
ƿilte of his land leode ƿollice ge neode. Ðe wære on ge-
fange beƿallan. 7 ƿadmaesse he lufode mid ealle. he læt
te mycel deop ƿið. 7 he lætde lasa ƿæri ƿið. 7 swa hwa swa
flose heofde. odde hinde. 7 hme man seolde blendian. he
ƿiðbead þa heofde. sƿiðe eac þa basas. swa sƿiðe lufode
þa hea deop. sƿiðe he ƿære heofde ƿæde. Eac he lætde be
þa hapian. 7 hi moƿten ƿeo. 7 apian. hit ƿære men hit
mendon. 7 þa earms men hit be ceopodan. Achr swa frid
7 þe ne ƿolte heofde eallra mid. ac hi moƿton mid ealle þe
cýnges ƿille ƿolgan 57 hi ƿoldon libban. odde land hab-
ban. land odde ealra. odde ƿel his sehta. Ða þa þe ænig
man seolde modigan swa. hme sƿiðe upp ahebban. 7 ofer
ealle men tellan. Ðe ælmihtiga god cýðe hit faule mid
heofde. 7 do hi sƿiðe ƿolgan. Ðal þing þe hab-
bad be hi geƿære. ærde ge geode ge ƿele. 7 þa godan
men innan ær heofde godnesse. 7 ƿolcon mid ealle

Old English

Prose:

– **Aelfric** (955-1005/1020??)

- Also known as "*the Grammarian*", the author of the homilies in Anglo-Saxon
- *Judith, Esther, Maccabees*
- Based on the Old Testament

– **Wulfstan:**

- Archbishop Wulfstan of York (d. 1023)
- wrote five Old English homilies on the last days:
 - *De Anticristo*
 - *Secundum Matheum*
 - *De Temporibus Anticristi*

De Anticristo

The Bayeux Tapestry

Middle English

1100-1500

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Middle English

The Battle of Hastings: 1066

- The **Battle of Hastings** → October 14th **1066** between Harold, King of England and William, Duke of Normandy
- 1051 → Edward the Confessor named William of Normandy heir to the English throne but January 1066, it was taken by Harold
- William landed on the beach at Pevensey with about 7,000 Bretons, Normans, French and Flemish troops.
- Harold was in the north, defeating the Vikings. N
- News reached him of the invasion and he hurried south.

Middle English

The Battle of Hastings

- Harold's men exhausted. Normans marched out of Hastings and took up positions on Telham Hill about a mile from Harold's camp.
- William made 1st attack and met with strong resistance. In the evening William made final attack, Harold was cut down by Norman swords and the Saxons defeated

Middle English

- Consequences:

- 1066 - **Harold II** is crowned king the day after Edward the Confessor dies
- William the Conqueror conquers England → Battle of Hastings **1066** → **William I**, first Norman King of England (to 1087)
- In **1070**, as penance, William had an abbey built on the site of the battle, with the high altar occupying the spot where Harold fell. The ruins of Battle Abbey, and the town of Battle, which grew up around it, remain

Harold dies

Battle Abbey

Middle English

William I (The Conqueror):

- William needed 6 years to consolidate his conquest
- constant plotting and fighting on both sides of the Channel (esp. Wales, Devon, Cornwall), he appointed earls
- **1069-70**: William defeated the Danes who attacked also the North
- **1072**: truce with Scotland (King Malcolm III) after several battles
- William built many defense **castles** (Windsor), up to 80 (Norman feudal order)
- He had some 5,000 knights at his disposal to repress rebellions
- expenses of numerous campaigns → William ordered a full-scale investigation → Domesday survey → **Domesday Book of 1086**
- *Anglo-Saxon Chronicle*: 'he was a very stern and violent man, so no one dared do anything contrary to his will ... Amongst other things the good security he made in this country is not to be forgotten.'
- **1087: William died** in Normandy, divided his reign among 3 sons:
 - Normandy for his eldest son Robert
 - England for William Rufus
 - His 3rd son Henry → 5,000 pounds in silver

William's Coronation

WINDSOR CASTLE

English ROYAL HOUSES

(You need to know them in chronological order)

The Normans

The Angevins

The Plantagenets

The Lancastrians

The Yorkists

The Tudors

Middle English

Significant Changes OE → ME:

- *Based on a comparison between a text in the 10th or 11th with one in the late 12th or 13th*
- 1. **OE diphthongs** become ME **monophthongs**:
heofonum → hevene (heaven)
- 2. New **diphthongs** emerge in ME:
dæg → *dai*, *day*
- 3. **Initial [h]** before consonants disappears in ME:
hræven → *raven*
- 4. [v,z] which were allophones in OE become **phonemes**
- 5. Unstressed vowels in the inflectional endings become **schwa** [ə]
- 6. The complete OE inflectional system is **simplified**

Middle English

Significant Changes OE → ME:

6. Loss of **strong** inflection of **adjectives**
7. Loss of grammatical **gender**
8. Emergence of the unified definite article '**the**'
9. Replacement of the case functions by a fixed word order and **prepositions**
10. First borrowing of **French** loan words
11. Increased emergence of **Scandinavian** loan words
12. Disappearance of the OE writing conventions:
ash, thorn, eth...
13. Increased use of **Latin** and Anglo Norman

Middle English

Transition from ME into eModE:

1. The first phase of the **Great Vowel Shift** is completed
2. **Unstressed** inflectional vowels become **mute**
3. Verb inflectional endings are reduced to [-s, -st, -th]
4. **London** English is more regarded as **standard**
5. Huge extension of the vocabulary by borrowing and word formation
6. First **printing press** in England by William **Caxton** in **1476**
7. Influence of the *Renaissance*
8. *Discovery of America*

Middle English

RISE & DECLINE of FRENCH in England

- for 200 years **French** → upper classes, mark of social distinction
- **English** → language of the masses
- Kings of England → dukes of Normandy
- English nobility was Anglo French aristocracy
- English always spoken, never abandoned
- In **1204** King **John** lost Normandy
- Separation of French & English nobilities
- By **1250** English nobility NOT Anglo French
- In **1337** '*The Hundred Years War*': English-French enemies
- French no longer used but great influence on English

Middle English

RISE & DECLINE of FRENCH in England

- Middle Ages → England was **bilingual**
- William Conqueror learnt English at 43 !!!
- His youngest son, **Henry** I, knew only some English
- Attitude of king and nobility towards English was of indifference until 1200
- Considerable body of literature in French produced in English (Anglo Norman)

Middle English

HELL

- 3 main **DIFFERENCES** between **OE** and **ME**:
 - Reduced system of grammatical inflections
 - Increased lexical borrowing from French and Latin
 - Highly varied and volatile orthography
- **No uniform** way of writing ME
 - *De Consolatione Philosophiae* by Boethius:
 - ‘First **woltow** suffre me to touche and assaye the estat of thy thought by a fewe demaundes, so that I may **understonde** what be the manere of thy curacioun?’
 - ‘First **wilt** thoug suffer me to touch and try the estate of thy thought by a few demands, so that I may **understand** what be the manner of thy curation?’
 - ‘First **will** you let me try the state of your thinking by asking a few questions, so that I can **understand** the way you cure people?’

Middle English

ME SPELLING:

- Style and script changed radically under the influence of **Norman French**
- OE spelling was stable and regular <> ME spelling varied greatly depending on place, person, period
- Many variants for the same word:
 - lief, lieif, leif, lefe, leue, leeue* → ‘leaf’
- **Ash, eth, wynn** and **yogh** went out of use in early ME
- **Thorn** remained longer until 15th c
- OE pronunciation of the 1st consonant in the cluster **cn-** continued with new spelling → **kn-**
 - Cnawan* → *knawan* → *to know*
- In late **ME k-** ceased to be pronounced but remained in the spelling:
 - Know, knee, knight* → *Silent Fossil K*

Middle English

ME SPELLING

– CONSONANTS

1. Some apparent innovations were older conventions:

Pre-OE	OE	ME
bef. 900		
<i>-th-</i>	<i>eth, thorn -th-</i>	
<i>uu [w]</i>	<i>wynn</i>	<i>w</i>

2. Others were real innovations:

OE	ME	IME	ModE
Yogh →	<i>y / gh</i>		
<i>Ʒeldan</i>	<i>Ʒeldan</i>	<i>yende(n)</i>	<i>to yield</i>
<i>cniht</i>	<i>cniƷt</i>	<i>knyght</i>	<i>knight</i>
<i>Ʒurh</i>	<i>ƷurƷ</i>	<i>thurgh</i>	<i>through</i>

3. After the Norman Conquest:

OE	ME (French infl.)
<i>Ʒ</i>	<i>g</i>

* In English *ge* & *gi* have same pronunciation as in French: *age, gem*

SCRIBE

Middle English

ME SPELLING

4. Consonant ‘v’ did not occur initially in English, ‘f’ was used as ‘v’ internally ex.: *driften* (=driven)

- No Standard English words of native origin began with v (except ‘*vixen*’)
- Words with initially ‘v’ come from Latin and French
- Anglo Norman scribes changed f → ‘v’
- Generally ‘v’ was used initially and ‘u’ elsewhere: *very*, *euer*

5. Consonant ‘c’ changed to ‘ch’ (palatal sound)

OE	ME
<i>cild</i>	<i>child</i>

* If this sound followed a short vowel it could be spelled ‘cch’ or ‘chch’:
cache, *cacche*, *cachche* (catch)

6. Consonants ‘sc’ changed to ‘sh’ (palatal sound):

OE	late OE	ME
<i>sceal</i>	<i>sceal</i>	<i>shall</i>
<i>/skeal/</i>	<i>/feal/</i>	

ME SPELLING:

Middle English

7. Consonants 'hw' → 'wh' progressively:

OE

hwæt

ME

what

8. Consonant 'c' was used for new sound /s/.

Before Normans: 'c' → [k] or [tʃ]

French: 'c' → [ts] → [s] (before e,i,y)

In ME 'c' → [k] (before a,o,u) ex. *cat, come*

→ [s] (before e,i) ex.: *city, cent*

* 'k' started to be used before e & i ex.: *cynn* → *kin, kyn*

9. Consonants 'cw' → 'qu' (French influence):

OE

cwellen

cwen

cweðan

ME

quellen

queen

quethen

ModE

kill

queen

say (quote)

10. Consonants 'cg' → 'gg' (French influence) → dg(e)

OE

ecg

ME

egge

ModE

edge

Courtly Love

Middle English

ME SPELLING

– VOWELS:

- To indicate vowel length, ME scribes used **double** letters (esp. in East Midland dialect): ee / oo
- But these sounds that survived do not indicate the same today → **ambiguous**:

ME

OE	ME	OE	ME	ModE
<i>ā</i>	<i>oo</i>	<i>rād</i>	<i>rood</i>	<i>rode</i>
<i>ō</i>	<i>oo</i>	<i>rōd</i>	<i>rood</i>	<i>rood</i>

Middle English

ME SPELLING

– VOWELS:

1. (**LENGHT**) Several devices to indicate vowel length:

a. Consonant + unstressed e

ME	ModE
<i>fode</i>	<i>food</i>
<i>fede</i>	<i>feed</i>

b. Double consonants indicated vowel length and also that preceding vowel was short:

dinner / diner

c. (Northern dialect) vowel + i → long sound

OE	ME	ModE
<i>rad</i>	<i>raid</i>	<i>raid</i>
<i>red</i>	<i>reid</i>	<i>Reid (name)</i>

Middle English

ME SPELLING

– VOWELS:

2. Short u → o if m,n,u (v,w) were contiguous:

<i>OE</i>	<i>ME</i>	<i>ModE</i>
<i>sunu</i>	<i>sonne</i>	<i>son</i>
<i>sunne</i>	<i>sonne</i>	<i>sun</i>

3. French ‘ou’ replaced OE long ū:

OE	ME
<i>hūs</i>	<i>hous</i>

* If ‘ou’ was found before a vowel, ‘u’ could be confused with ‘v’. So, ‘u’ was doubled in this position: ‘uu’ and later → w

douer → *douuer* → *dower* / *douer* → *Dover*

4. ME scribes used ‘y’ for the semivowel [y] and as a variant of ‘i’. Late in ME, tendency to write ‘y’ for long ‘i’ and ‘y’ also in final position.

5. ME spelling was much more relaxed than today’s:

<i>speach</i>	<i>water</i>	<i>treese</i>
<i>speech</i>	<i>watter</i>	<i>tres</i>

ME DIALECTS & RISE of a LONDON Standard:

There were many
different accents but 4
major dialects:

Northern

East Midland

West Midland

Southern

Middle English

Middle English

- **Dialect Differences:**

- **Plural pronouns**

Northern **they, their, them**

Midlands **they, hir, hem**

Southern **hi, hir, hem**

- **verb 3 pers. sing**

Northern **-s (e.g. hits)**

Midlands **-th (i.e. hitteth)**

Southern **-th (i.e. hitteth)**

- **verb pl.**

Northern **-s (i.e. hits)**

Midlands **-en (i.e., hitten)**

Southern **-eth (i.e., hitteth)**

- **Present participle:**

Nothern **-ande (i.e.lovande)**

Midlands **-ende (i.e. lovende)**

Southern **-inde (i.e. lovinde)**

Middle English

Dialect Differences

- *Old English long o:*

Northern **a** (e.g., **stan**)

Midlands **o** (**stone**)

Southern **o** (**stone**)

- *Old English c*

Northern **k** (**ik, kirk**)

Midlands **ch** (**ich, chirch**)

Southern **ch** (**church**)

- *Old English f :*

Northern **f** (**fox**)

Midlands **f** (**fox**)

Southern **v** (**vox**)

Middle English

- Generally Southern more conservative and Northern more innovative
- End of 14th → emerged a written language
→ East Midland (**London**) → Standard English:
 1. Less conservative than south and less radical than North
 2. Largest, richest, most populous area
 3. Presence of **universities** (Oxford, Cambridge)

Middle English

- **Chaucer's** influence? His style different from official documents. Chaucer used language of poetry
→ more **conservative**
- Standard based on official records → **London**
- **London:**
 - Commercial center → businessmen brought London accent everywhere
 - Started as Southern and ended as Midland dialect
 - Influence of **Chancery** clerks
 - 1476 → Printing Press, William Caxton in London.
 - End of 15th London accepted as 'standard' in writing

Middle English

CONSONANTAL CHANGES in ME:

- Consonants have been quite stable in history <> vowels
- ME consonants: b,d,k,l,m,n,p,r,s,t, þ (ð),w, x [ks]

f: [f] / [v] ȝ: [g] / [y] g: [h] / [χ]

- Most important changes are:

1. OE sequences **hl, hn and hr** → simplified:

OE → ME ModE OE → ME ModE

hl l hn n

hleapan lepen leap hnutu nute nut

OE → ME

hr r

hraðor rather

OE → ME

hw wh North kept it

South reduced to w

Middle English

CONSONANTAL CHANGES in ME:

2. OE voiced fricative **g** after **l**, **r** → **w**:

<i>OE</i>	<i>ME</i>	<i>ModE</i>
<i>halgian</i>	<i>halwen</i>	<i>hallow</i>

3. Consonant (s or t) + **w** + back vowel → **w** is lost:

<i>OE</i>	<i>ME</i>	<i>ModE</i>
<i>twa</i>	<i>ta</i>	<i>to</i>

* In OE times **w** had been lost in negatives: *we + wille* → *nille*

* Silent **w** in ModE: two, sword, answer ...

4. ‘**ch**’ was lost in unstressed syllables:

<i>OE</i>	<i>ME</i>	<i>ModE</i>
<i>-lic</i>	<i>-ly</i>	<i>-ly</i> <i>quickly, softly</i>
<i>-liche</i>		

Middle English

CONSONANTAL CHANGES in ME:

5. ‘v’ was lost before a consonant (an e might appear)

<i>OE</i>	<i>ME</i>	<i>ModE</i>
<i>heafod</i>	<i>heved, hevd, hed</i>	<i>head</i>
<i>hlaford</i>	<i>loverd</i>	<i>lord</i>

6. OE prefix *-ge* → *i-* (*y-*):

<i>OE</i>	<i>ME</i>	<i>ModE</i>
<i>gewiss</i>	<i>iwiss</i>	<i>certain</i>

7. Initial *f*, *s* and thorn (*þ*) were voiced in the South:

v → *f* *s* → *z* *þ* → *ð*

Middle English

CONSONANTAL CHANGES in ME:

8. Final inflectional *n* was lost, and final *n* of unstressed possessive pronouns *mīn* and *þīn*:

<i>OE</i>	<i>ME</i>	<i>ModE</i>
<i>mīn fæder</i>	<i>my fader</i>	<i>my father</i>

* *an ekename* → *a nekename* → *a nickname*

9. Voiced fricatives that were OE allophones → phonemes with the introduction of French words and words beginning with [v]:

<i>OE</i>	<i>ME</i>	<i>late ME</i> (loss of final <i>-e</i>)
<i>-fe</i>	<i>-ve</i>	<i>-v</i>
<i>-se</i>	<i>-ze</i>	<i>-z</i>
<i>-þe</i>	<i>-ðe</i>	<i>-ð</i>

Middle English

VOWEL CHANGES:

1. OE **long vowel** sounds ē ī ō ū remained unchanged but different spelling:

<i>OE</i>	<i>ME</i>	<i>ModE</i>
<i>fēt</i>	<i>fēt</i>	<i>feet</i>
<i>rīdan</i>	<i>rīden</i>	<i>ride</i>
<i>hūs</i>	<i>hōus</i>	<i>house</i>

2. Except for OE ash (æ) and y, OE **short vowels** of stressed syllables → unchanged in ME:

<i>OE</i>	<i>ME</i>	<i>ModE</i>
<i>wascan</i>	<i>washen</i>	<i>wash</i>
<i>helpan</i>	<i>helpen</i>	<i>help</i>

3. OE **long y** → unrounding to long [ī] in North and East Midland:

Middle English

VOWEL CHANGES:

4. OE long a [ā] → unchanged in North: hām, rāp ...

→ became [e] in Mod Scots: *hame, rape...*

→ became long open rounded o [ɔ], spelled o, oo

South of Humber

OE	ME	ModE
[ā]	long open [ɔ]	o (oo)
[ō]	long close [ō]	o (oo)

*	ME		ModE	
	long open	[ɔ]	←	[o] { o + e: <i>rode</i> oa: <i>road</i>
	close open	[ō]	←	oo { [u:]: <i>food</i> [u]: <i>foot</i> [ʌ]: <i>flood</i>

Middle English

VOWEL CHANGES:

5. OE **long ash** → ME long open e [ɛ], spelled e or ee (= [e])

	ME		ModE
North of Thames	long [ɛ]	→	ea
	[e]	→	e (ee)

6. OE **short ash** fell together with short a → spelled a in ME:

OE		ME
<i>glæd</i>	→	<i>glad</i>

* Except in the South: *gled*

7. OE **short y** → unrounding in North and East:

OE		ME	
y	→	i	North and East Midland
y	→	e	Southeast
y	→	u [ü]	Southwest and West Midland

Middle English

ME DIPHTHONGS:

1. OE diphtongs disappeared, new ones emerged

2. OE long ea [eā] → long open e [ɛ] **smoothing**

long eo [eō] → long close e [e] (11th c)

OE	ME	} ModE	
leāf	leaf		leaf
seōn	seen		see

3. **Two new ditphthongs** ending in glide [i]: **ai / ei**

* *Sources:*

a) vocalization of g to i after front vowels

OE	ME	ModE
sægde	saide	said
weg	wey	way

b) development of an i-glide between a front vowel and OE h

OE	ME	ModE
ehta	eighte	eight

ME DIPHTHONGS:

4. Four new ME diphthongs in glide [u]:

[u] → [au] [ɔu] [ɛu] [iu]

*Sources:

a) vocalization of g to u after back vowels:

OE	ME	ModE
sagu	sawe	saw
boga	bowe	bow

b) development of a u-glide between a back vowel and OE h:

OE	ME	ModE
āht	aught	aught
brohte	broughte	brought

c) w after a vowel became a u-glide:

OE	ME	ModE
clawu	clawe	calw
grōwan	growen	grow

5. Two new ME diphthongs of French origin:

	ME	ModE
[ɔi]: oi, oy	joie, cloistre	joy, cloister
[ui]: oi, oy	poisen, joinen	boil, join

Middle English

LEVELLING of UNSTRESSED VOWELS

- OE vowels merged into **schwa** sound, spelled **e**:

	OE	ME
o	lama	lame
a	nacod	naked
u	medu	mede (liquor)

o } e [ə]
a }
u }

- **Loss of final** schwa in final syllables, levelled final **e** [ə] gradually lost in North (13th c), Midlands and South later.
- **Non-final** unstressed **e** (written i,y,u in some dialects) was lost when there was an inflectional ending, except after sibilants: maketh → makth
- The vowel sound was retained in ‘-ed’ until 15th c. It has not yet disappeared in the forms: *aged, blassed, learned* when used as adjectives.

Middle English

GRAMMAR CHANGES

– Reduction of inflection:

- Leveling (merging of unstressed vowels) caused reduction in forms. ME had few inflectional distinctions.
- In adj. gender distinguishing masc. was lost

Maculine Nominative

–a

e

Neuter Nom-Acc. & Fem. Nom. -e

OE

Se ealda man (masc)

Seo ealde talu (fem)

þæt ealde swurd

ME

the olde man

the olde tale

the olde sword

Middle English

GRAMMAR CHANGES

- OE weak **adjectives** endings merged into -e:
-an / -um > -en → (loss of 'n') → -e
- OE **genitive** plural forms of weak adjectives merged into -e:
-ena → -ene → -e / -ra → re → -e
- Thus, 5 sing. + plural forms of OE weak adj. were reduced to 'e'.
- **Number** and **gender** distinctions → **lost**
- Effects of leveling were far reaching:

- endings of infinitives: -an
 - endings of indicative past plural: -on
 - endings of past participles: -en
- } -en

* Result: endingless verbs in ModE

	OE	ME	ModE
Infin.	<i>Findan</i>	<i>finden</i>	<i>find</i>
Past Pl.	<i>Findon</i>	<i>founde(n)</i>	<i>found</i>
Past Part.	<i>Finden</i>	<i>founde(n)</i>	<i>found</i>

GRAMMAR CHANGES

1. THE NOUN:

- Inflectional endings considerably reduced:

1st Declension

	OE		ME
sing	plural		
mūð	mūðas	→	mūð
mūðes	mūða	→	mūðes
mūðe	mūðum	→	mūðe

- -e was organic in: the dative sing, genit. plural, dative plural
- This -e was extended to nom. + acc. sing-. → stōne, mūðe
- The only distinction was ‘-s’ or poss. sing. and nom. + acc. plural
- Thus, ‘-s’ became the mark of **PLURALITY**
- In early ME 2 methods of plurality:
 - s or -es for strong declension
 - en for weak declension
- Until 13th c plural ‘-en’ was most used in South, but rest of Engln ‘-s’.
- By the end of **14th c**, ‘-s’ accepted all over England as mark of plurality

Middle English

GRAMMAR CHANGES

2. PRONOUNS:

- General decay of inflections in nouns and adj. made it necessary to rely more upon juxtaposition, word order + use of prepositions to make clear relation of words in a sentence
- **DEMONSTRATIVES:** greatest loss of f inflections

OE		ME	OE		ME	
sē	}	the / that	þēs	}	<i>sing.</i>	<i>pl.</i>
seō			þēos		þis	those
þæt			þis			these

- **PERSONAL PRONOUNS:**

- No great losses because of need for different forms for Gender and Case (*I, me, my, etc*)
- Dative + Accusative → Dative
- Dual number (*wit, git*)

GRAMMAR CHANGES

3. ADJECTIVES:

- Weak adjectives lost inflections
- By 1250 strong adj. only had different forms (sing. + pl.) for monosyllabic which ended in consonants: glad (sing), glade (pl.)

• COMPARATIVES

OE
-ra → ME
-re > -er

* caused by leveling

* if the root vowel of an adj. was long it was shortened before these endings: swet → swetter / swettest (later, original length was restored)

SUPERLATIVES

OE
-ost / -est → ME
-est

• IRREGULARS:

	<i>Comparative</i>	<i>Superlatives</i>
badde (ēvel)	werse	werst
gōd	bettre / er	best
muchel	mōre	mōst
lītel	lesse / lasse	lēste
ōld	eldre /er	eldest

4. VERBS:

- **General tendency:**

1. Leveling of inflections
2. Weakening of endings
3. Loss of strong conjugation (irregulars)

- New verbs became **weak** (dental suffix) after Norman Conquest
- More than ½ of strong verbs have disappeared (→ weak)

- **Gradual changes:**
- | <i>strong Past</i> | <i>weak Past</i> |
|--------------------|-------------------------|
| <i>ache</i> | <i>oke</i> <i>ached</i> |

- Many forms used simultaneously:

Strong	Weak	
<i>stope</i>	<i>stepped</i>	<i>stoped</i>
<i>rewe</i>	<i>rowed</i>	<i>rowed</i>
<i>shove</i>	<i>shaved</i>	<i>shaved</i>

- **Weak** forms usually won out, but not always (blowed / blew or knowed / knew)
- Some forms continue today (spelt / spelled or cleft / clove)
- There are 68 OE strong verbs in use today, 81 have become weak and 13 have both forms

Durham

Early Modern English

William Shakespeare

Unit 4

Early Modern English

- **Henry VIII**

- He was a lavish patron of the arts
- He wrote a book attacking Martin Luther and supporting the Roman Catholic church, in 1521 Henry was given the title 'Defender of the Faith' by the Pope.
- Henry's interest in foreign policy was focused on Western Europe, esp. France & Spain
- unsuccessful Anglo-Spanish campaigns against France, ending in peace with France in 1520
- second half of Henry's reign was dominated by the Protestant Reformation

Henry VIII

1509-1547

**The Tudors
1485-1603**

Early Modern English

Henry VIII and his 6 wives

The Tudors
1485-1603

1. Catherine of Aragon

2. Anne Boleyn

3. Jane Seymour

4. Anne Cleves

5. Katherine Howard

6. Catherine Parr

Early Modern English

**Queen Mary I
1553-1558**

**The Tudors
1485-1603**

- Jane reigned for only 9 days and was later executed with her husband in 1554.
- the country wanted **Mary**, Catherine of Aragon's daughter and a devout Roman Catholic as Queen. She was courageous and stubborn
- Restored papal supremacy in England, abandoned the title of Supreme Head of the Church, reintroduced **Roman Catholic** bishops and began the slow reintroduction of monastic orders (**heresy persecuted**, 300 Protestants executed → Cranmer)
- She was **37 years** at her accession, wished to marry and have children, thus leaving a Catholic heir, and removing half-sister Elizabeth (focus for Protestant opposition) from direct succession.
- Mary's decision to marry **Philip, King of Spain**, in 1554 was very unpopular
- The marriage was **childless**, Philip spent most of it on the continent, England obtained no share in the Spanish monopolies in New World trade and the alliance with Spain dragged England into a war with France
- **1558: Mary** died (cancer?) → crown to her half-sister **Elizabeth**.

- Last **Tudor** monarch
- daughter of Henry VIII and his second wife, Anne Boleyn.
- She was 3rd in line, behind Prince Edward and Princess Mary
- **1558**- Mary died, Elizabeth → Queen of England
- Good education (fluent in 6 languages)
- **45-year** reign considered one of the most glorious in English history , also called ‘**Virgin Queen**’ (→ Virginia)

Queen
Elizabeth I
1558-1603

- the arts flourished during Elizabeth's reign: Queen attended 1st performance of Shakespeare's '*A Midsummer Night's Dream*'
- She toured the country in regional visits known as '**progresses**' (25)
- **Dangers**: threats of invasion from Spain through Ireland, and from France through Scotland.
- she passed harsh laws against Roman Catholics

Queen
Elizabeth I
1558-1603

The Tudors
1485-1603

Early Modern English

- Plots to assassinate her → Mary, Queen of Scots, executed in 1587
- **1588** → defeat (bad weather??)
The Spanish Armada → high costs → economic depression → people suffered
- Elizabeth chose never to marry
- She said she married her country ‘personal sacrifice for the good of the nation’ → very popular
- died at Richmond Palace on 24 March 1603

Queen
Elizabeth I
1558-1603

• **The Spanish Armada**, also the ‘**Invincible Armada**’

– 1588. Philip II prepared the Armada that, with the help of the Spanish Army in the Netherlands → conquer England:

- England helped Protestants rebels in Europe (Netherlands)
- English pirates and mercenaries (Francis Drake) attacked Spanish ships on their way back from the Americas (robbed gold)

King Philip

Francis Drake

Plan:

- Bring together large army of soldiers in the Netherlands under the **Duke of Parma** and get them ready for invasion.
- Using a large fleet of ships, carry extra fighting men & equipment from Spain to the Straits of Dover and join up with the Duke of Parma's army
- Win control of the English Channel and protect the Duke of Parma's army as it crossed the Straits of Dover to England
- Invade England and force Queen Elizabeth to agree to Spain's demands
 - 1. Allow English Catholics to worship God in the way they wanted; 2. Stop helping the Dutch rebels in the Spanish Netherlands; and 3. Hand over money to Spain to pay for the cost of the invasion

Queen Elizabeth

The Duke of Parma

Early Modern English

- Born in Edinburgh Castle 19 July 1566, only son of Mary, **Queen of Scots** (2nd husband, Lord Darnley)
- 13 months old → crowned **King of Scots** in Stirling
- Childhood → constant struggles of the nobles → 4 successive regents
- great ambition was to succeed Elizabeth I on the throne of England
- 1587 → he married **Anne of Denmark**
- On 24 March **1603** James inherited the throne of England (Queen Elizabeth died)
- He wanted 2 kingdoms united but Scotland retained its own parliament, established Church and legal and educational systems.
- died on 27 March **1625**.
- **1603**: designed British flag by combining England's red cross of St. George with Scotland's white cross of St. Andrew

James I (England)
& VI (Scotland)

1603–1625

STUARTS

Early Modern English

KING JAMES BIBLE (1611)

- He sponsored translation of the *Authorized King James Version of the Bible*
- appointed the world's best **scholars** and paid careful attention to ensure that the translation was completed
- Work began in **1604**, 47 translators organized into 6 groups: Westminster, Cambridge, Oxford, general rules for all groups, **completed in 1611 !!**
 - The Authorized Version eclipsed all previous versions of the Bible

THE SECOND EPISTLE

of Paul the apostle to the

Thessalonians.

CHAP. I.

- 1 Saint Paul certifieth them of the good opinion which he had of their faith, love, and patience: 11 And therewithall useth divers reasons for the comforting of them in persecution, whereof the chiefest is taken from the righteous judgement of God.

Paul and Silvanus, and Timotheus unto the church of the Thessalonians, in God our Father, & the Lord Jesus Christ:

2 Grace unto you, and peace from God our Father, and the Lord Jesus Christ.

3 We are bound to thank God alwayes for you, brethren, as it is meet, because that your faith groweth exceedingly, and the charitie of every one of you all towards each other aboundeth:

4 So that we our selbes glorie in you in the churches of God, for your patience and faith in all your persecutions and tribulations that ye endure:

5 Which is a manifest token of the righteous judgement of God, that ye may be counted worthy of the kingdom of God, for which ye also suffer;

6 Seeing it is a righteous thing with God to recompense tribulation to them that trouble you:

7 And to you who are troubled, rest with us, when the Lord Jesus shall be revealed from heaven, † with his mighty angels,

8 In flaming fire, || taking vengeance on them that know not God, and that obey not the gospel of our Lord Jesus Christ,

9 who shall be punished with everlasting destruction from the presence of

the Lord, and from the glory of his power:

10 when he shall come to be glorified in his saints, and to be admired in all them that beleebe (because our testimonye among you was beleebed) in that day.

11 wherefore also we pray alwayes for you, that our God would || count you worthy of this calling, and fulfill all the good pleasure of his goodnesse, and the work of faith with power:

12 That the Name of our Lord Jesus Christ may be glorified in you, and ye in him, according to the grace of our God, and the Lord Jesus Christ.

CHAP. II.

- 1 He willet them to continue stedfast in the truth received, 3 sheweth that there shall be a departure from the faith, 9 and a discovery of Antichrist, before the day of the Lord come. 15 And thereupon repeateth his former exhortation, and prayeth for them.

Now we beseech you, brethren, by the coming of our Lord Jesus Christ, and by our gathering together unto him,

2 That ye be not soon shaken in minde, or be troubled, neither by spirit, nor by word, nor by letter, as from us, as that the day of Christ is at hand.

3 Let no man deceive you by any means; for that day shall not come, except there come a falling away first, and that man of sin be revealed, the son of perdition,

4 who opposeth and exalteth himselfe above all that is called God, or that is worshipped: so that he as God, sitteth in the temple of God, shewing himself that he is God.

5 Remember ye not, that when I was yet with you, I told you these things:

2 Thessalonians 1:1 to 2:5

6 And

† Greek, the angels of his power.
|| Or, yeelding.

|| Or, safe.

Early Modern English

EModE Orthography

- **Great Vowel Shift** → greatest and most important phonological change in the history of English
- Yet OE spelling was maintained ‘cause printers based spelling on medieval manuscripts, not on new pronunciation

Middle Eng. **Modern Eng**

ex.: *feet* [e] *feet* [i:]

- Learned men preferred an archaic spelling
 - ‘y’ used as ‘th’ → ‘y[†]’ as an abbrev. of ‘that’
y e as an abbrev. of ‘the’ → Ye Olde Shoppe
 - ‘i’ as a vowel and ‘j’ as a consonant not established until 17th c (King James Bible and Shakespeare)

Early Modern English

- The ‘h’ sound was lost in Late Latin, but French scribes influenced by classical Latin restored it in the spelling of many words although not pronounced
- Renaissance → ‘h’ was put after ‘t’ in many foreign words

Greek	Latin	Old French	English
›	<i>thronus</i>	<i>trone</i>	<i>throne</i>

also in: *theatre, thesis, anthem, Anthony ...*

- * In Latin and French the ‘h’ was not pronounced, but later in English it began to be pronounced

- Other Renaissance respellings:

det → *debt* (Lat. *debitum*)

dout → *doubt* (Lat. *dubitare*)

indit → *indict*

sutle → *subtle*

in all these examples
the pronunciation
was not affected

- * In some cases the pronunciation was affected: *faut* → *fault*

Early Modern English

Otto
Jespersen
"Discoverer"
of the GV S

THE GREAT VOWEL SHIFT (GVS)

- All ME long vowels underwent great changes
- Short vowels in accented syllables remained relatively stable, only the short **a** and the short **u** changed

Chaucer

Shakespeare

a → æ (ash) ex.: *thanks, cat, at ...*

u → unrounded u ex.: *full, but*

- Great Vowel Shift was a massive sound change affecting the long vowels during the fifteenth to eighteenth centuries
- Basically, GVS = **all long vowels that could be raised were raised one level in the mouth**

- Some linguists have described the GVS as a ‘chain reaction’, i.e., as **drag chains** or **push chains** (the French linguist André Martinet coined the French terms *chaîne de traction* and *chaîne de propulsion*).

Early Modern English

THE GREAT VOWEL SHIFT (GVS)

Drag Chain

Step 1: i and u drop and become θI and θU

Step 2: e and o move up, becoming i and u

Step 3: a moves forward to æ

Step 4: ϵ becomes e, ɔ becomes o

Step 5: æ moves up to e

Step 6: e moves up to i

A new e was created in Step 4; now that e moves up to i.

Step 7: ϵ moves up to e

The new ϵ created in Step 5 now moves up.

Step 8: θI and θU drop to aI and aU

the pronunciation of vowels in many words was raised to a higher tongue position: *eny* became pronounced *any* [enny], *here* [heir *hair*] became pronounced *here* [hir *hear*], *hi:re* [hir *hear*] became pronounced *hire* [hair *higher*], *wind* [wi:nd] became *wind* [waɪnd], *tool* [tall] became pronounced *tool* [tu:l], and *tu:n* [*tune*] became pronounced *town* [taun]

Early Modern English

Push

Chain

The Great Vowel Shift

(Involving Long Vowels Only)

Retention of Short Vowels

- /a:/ -> /ei/ (in e.g. *make*)
- /e:/ -> /i:/ (in e.g. 'feet)
- /i:/ -> /ai/ (in e.g. *mice*)
- /o:/ -> /u:/ (in e.g. *boot*)
- /u:/ -> /au/ (in e.g. *mouse*)

Early Modern English

Prof. Menzer's **Eight-Step Pull Chain** theory

**GVS
Timeline**

http://www.alturapaint.com/gvs_folders/primary_pages/gvs.htm#

Why did the GVS happen?

* **Why did the pronunciation of /i/ and /u/ change in the first place — setting the whole GVS in motion?**

- No recordings of that time. So, linguists don't really know the exact reasons
- We know it happened because 'uneducated' people would usually write out words that they did not know phonetically

Recent research:

- the traditional analogy describes links in a chain causing the others to move when pulled
- 1980s → textual evidence and dialectal survey material, new theory → **2 separate shifts** occurring (1st from 1450 to 1550 and 2nd from 1650 to 1750) which belonged to two different parts of the country. These two separate shifts then merged due to repeated exposure in mixed contexts of commerce and trade.
 - * This could explain why some of the monophthong vowels shifted places and became different monophthongs, while other monophthong vowels shifted and became diphthongs (*Crystal*)

Early Modern English

• CONSONANTAL CHANGES:

1. [ç] voiceless palatal fricative next to front vowels disappears (no longer pronounced) but present in spelling ex. *bright, sigh, weigh*
2. [x] voiceless velar fricative next to back vowels disappeared or became voiceless labiodental fricative [f] ex.: *cough, laugh, enough*
3. [b] in 'al' before consonants was lost after 1st becoming a vowel. ME 'al' & 'au' fell together al + au → au → [] ex.: *talk, walk*
 - * except before 'f', 'v' and 'm'
 - 'al' → [a:] or [æ] ex.: *half, calm*
 - * [l] in 'ol' also lost before some consonants ex.: *folk, Holmes*

Early Modern English

- **CONSONANTAL CHANGES:**

4. ‘h’ In French loanwords like *host*, *humble*, ‘h’ has come to be pronounced. In other words not pronounced

ex.: *honest, hour, heir, honor*

5. ‘-ing’ when unstressed had long been pronounced [in]. The velarization of [n] to [ŋ] began as hypercorrection in 1st quarter of 19th c

Early Modern English

- **STRESS Changes:**
 1. Great variety in stress (Shakespeare's rhymes)
 2. Many words stressed differently ex.: *illústrate*, *concéntrate*, *charácter*, *contémplate*
 3. Most polysyllabic words ending in –able, -ible had initial stress and second stress on penultimate syllable
 4. Most words with final stress now had initial stress ex.: *ántique*, *cómplete*

Early Modern English

GRAMMAR CHANGES:

1. NOUNS

- By end of ME ‘-es’ was **genitive** singular and caseless plural suffix. Most nouns had only 2 forms (*sister/sisters*) as today.
 - * use of apostrophe for genitive singular (*sister’s*) and plural (*sisters’*) not adopted until the **17th** and **18th** c respectively
- **Irregular plurals:** mutated vowel plurals resisted analogical principle: *feet, geese, teeth, lice, mice, men, women*
- A few ‘-n’ plurals remained: *eyen (eyes), shoon (shoes), kine (cows)* and *brethren (borthers), children, oxen*
 - * *kine, brethren* and *children* had no ‘-n’ in OE !!!
 - * **Oxen** is the only **pure survival** of OE weak declension

Early Modern English

1. NOUNS

- **Uninflected plurals** (words which have same form in sing. and plural)) survive today
ex.: *deer, sheep, swine, folk, kind*
* analogical ‘folks’ occurred early in ModE, kind has acquired ‘s’ plural
- **His-genitive**: use of his, her, their as signs of genitive began in OE ex.: *Augustus his daughter* → *Augustus’ daughter* in 16th-17th c
- **Group genitive**: developed in early ModE ex. *The tale of the Wife of Bath* → *The Wife of Bath’s Tale*
* also 2 nouns: ‘*an hour or two’s time*’
- **Uninflected genitive**: in special circumstances, esp. nouns ending in [s] or before [s] ex.: *For God sake*

Early Modern English

2. ADJECTIVES

- Distinction between strong and weak adj. simplified, but loss of –n and schwa
- **Demonstratives** only adj. (*this / these, that / those*) that agree in number with nouns.
- Comparatives formed with ‘-er’ and superlatives with ‘-est’, but increasing use of ‘more’ and ‘most’
 - **No clear rules** for ‘-er’ / ‘more’ ex.: *more poor, more better, beautifuler*

3. ADVERBS

- Many adverbs with **no adverbial mark** (no –ly). Today this is ‘bad English’ ex.: *indifferent cold, grievous sick*

Early Modern English

4. PRONOUNS.

- Several changes, but are the most inflected grammatical category

a) Personal Pronouns

Nom.	<i>I</i>	<i>thou</i>	<i>he, a</i>	<i>(h)it</i>	<i>she</i>
Objective	<i>me</i>	<i>thee</i>	<i>him</i>	<i>(h)it</i>	<i>her</i>
Possesive	<i>my/mine</i>	<i>thy/thine</i>	<i>his</i>	<i>it,its</i>	<i>hers</i>

Nom.	<i>we</i>	<i>ye/you</i>	<i>they</i>
Object.	<i>us</i>	<i>you/ye</i>	<i>them, (h)em</i>
Possesive	<i>our/ours</i>	<i>your/yours</i>	<i>their/theirs</i>

Early Modern English

4. PRONOUNS.

a) Personal Pronouns

- ‘I’ was capitalized because ‘i’ was overlooked
- **My / thy** (before consonants) ex.: *my crown*
mine / thine (before vowel, h, pause) ex. *mine eyes*
- **Thou, thee, thy, thyne** → ‘thoute’ form (**tutear**)
You, ye, your (**Usted**) and for plural
Finally, all classes adopted you (usted) forms in 18th c
!!
- ‘he’ was written ‘a’ when unstressed
- ‘hit’ and ‘it’ coexisted
- Regal ‘we’ used for single person → today Queen still says ‘*we think that ...*’

Early Modern English

4. PRONOUNS:

b) Relative Pronouns

OE	ME	ModE (16th c)
<i>þe</i>	<i>that / which</i>	<i>who</i>

- No concern for proper choice until 17th c → prescriptivists
- Nominative after ‘as’ and ‘than’
ex.: *She is as tall as I*
- **Nominative** with ‘and’:
ex.: *between you and I*
* still not consistent today
- Use of ‘**who**’ and ‘**whom**’ indiscriminate

Early Modern English

5. VERBS:

- Many **strong** verbs became **weak** or were lost
- **4 verbal** forms (infinitive, past sing./plural, participle) reduced to **3**
- Verbal endings simplified:

ME

ich sitte

to sitten

ModE

I sit

to sit

- Some ModE verbs had endings now lost

Present

I sit

thou sittest, sits

he she sitteth, sits

we you they sit

Past

I he we you they sat

thou sat, satest, satst

Unit 5

Contemporary English

Contemporary English

- **British Isles** = UK + Ireland
- **UK** = Britain + Northern Ireland
- **Britain**: England, Scotland & Wales
- **4 major dialectal areas:**
 - EngEng
 - ScotEng
 - WalEng
 - IrEng (North & South)

Contemporary English

- English **Dialects & Accents:**

- Based on historical dialects (Northumbria, Mercia, Midlands, etc)
- **Dialect:** grammatical and **lexical** variation
- **Accent:** phonological variation
- Most prestigious BrEng accent today → **RP**, also **BBC English** or **Queen's English**

Contemporary English

• Northern dialects

(=Scotland):

- rhotic area
- pairs of words like *put* / *putt* → homophonous and ‘*bus*’, ‘*must*’ or ‘*but*’ sound /u/
- open vowel ‘o’, *long* → /lang/
- diphthong /ai/ in *night*, *time* have older pronunciation /nit/ / tim/
- no diphthong /ou/ in *house* → /hu:s/
- no long vowel ‘oo’ in *spoon* → /spjun/

Contemporary English

- **Midland dialects:**

- Partly northern, partly southern
- pairs of words like *put* / *putt* → homophonous and ‘*bus*’, ‘*must*’ or ‘*but*’ sound /u/
- pronounce *-ing* in west midlands more than east (*dancing*, *singing*)
- some rhotic areas
- *you* is /jau/
- Few glotal stops

Contemporary English

• Southern dialects:

Southwest:

- voicing of ‘s’ to ‘z’: *I zee* (see), *I zay* (say)
- Voicing of ‘f’ to ‘v’: *the varmer* (farmer)
- ‘t’ is pronounced ‘d’ in *city*, *better*
- rounded u in *boot*, *rude* /ü/

Southeast:

- More similar to RP
- Some diphthongs different: /ei/ → /ai/ in *Spain*, *rain*, *plain*
- Loss of ‘l’ at the end of words like *school*, *fool*, *Paul*
- /p,t,k/ heavily aspirated
- Glottal stop very common
- /h/ is sometimes lost (=cockney)

Contemporary English

- Traditionally several **regional dialects**, most typical: **Northern** and **Southwest** dialects

- Also ‘**urban dialects**’ → cities:

- **Geordie** (Newcastle)
- **Glaswegian** (Glasgow)
- **Scouse** (Liverpool)
- **Birmingham** (Brummie)
- **Cockney** (London)

Contemporary English

- **Glaswegian** (Scotland):

- influence from Scots & Irish English
- stigmatized → ‘corrupt, debased’, etc

Pronunciation:

- ‘the’ → ‘ra’, ra polis (te police), ramorra (tomorrow), murra (mother)
- unstressed final / / in fella (fellow), Glesca (Glasgow), awfa (awful), yisfa (useful)
- ‘d’ is lost after /l/ and /n/: caul (cold), roon (round), win (wind)

Contemporary English

- **Glaswegian** (Scotland):

- negative: *-nae*, *-ny* as in *cannae* (can't), *dinnae* (don't)
- (Ulster origin) 2nd personal pronoun plural form: *youse*, *yese*, *yiz*

Vocabulary:

- *bam*, *bampot*, *bamstick* = idiot
- *boggin*, *bowfin* = smelly
- *hairy*, *herry*, *hingoot* = girl
- *stocious* = drunk
- *nooky* = sexual intercourse

Contemporary English

- **Scouse (Liverpool):**

- working-class accent, influence from Ireland & Wales → stigmatized

Pronunciation:

- alveolar 'r' (rhotic)
- intervocalic 't' replaced sometimes by 'r' → *marra* (matter)
- confusion of some consonants /t,d/ in *these three /dese tree/*
- flat intonation

Contemporary English

- **Geordie** (Newcastle)

Pronunciation:

- non-rhotic, initial 'h' not dropped
- strong **glottal stop** in final position or before weak vowel (city, local)
- /o/ vowel in *know*, *goat*

Grammar:

- *Aa* (I) → *Aa don't know*
- *diven't / don't*: *I diven't do nothing* (I don't do anything)

Vocabulary:

- *bonny lad / lass* = boy / girl
- *hinny* (honey): form of address

Contemporary English

- **Cockney** (London):

- origin: 18th c, used in London, esp. East-End part (working class)

Pronunciation:

- glottal stop for medial and final /t/ and /k/: *butter*
- Non-rhotic but Linking 'r'
- /f/ for 'th' as in /firty fahsn/ *thirty thousand* and v for th in /muvver/ *mother*
- no initial h: *house* /aus/
- Diphthongs: /ai/ for /ei/ in *Spain*; /oi/ for /ai/ in *right*; /a/ for /au/ in *about*

Contemporary English

- **Cockney** (London):

Grammar

- double negation
- *done* = did and *seen* = saw: *I done it yesterday*

Vocabulary:

- rhyming slang: *Would you Adam and Eve it? (believe it?)* and back slang: yob (boy)
- phrases: Gawdelpus (God help us!)
- from Romany: chavvy (child), mush (mate)
- from Yiddish: schlemiel (fool)

N United States

Unit 6

AMERICAN ENGLISH

Pacific Ocean

Atlantic Ocean

- Northern Mariana Islands
- Guam
- American Samoa

- U.S. Virgin Islands
- Puerto Rico

American English

American English

UNITED STATES OF AMERICA POLITICAL-GEOGRAPHIC DIVISIONS

American English

- English → 1 lang. with several national variations: UKEng., USEng., IREng., CanEng., AusEng., etc
- British English → greater prestige in the world
 - False concepts: ‘purity’, ‘elegance’, ‘style’ but What is British English? RP, BBC English, Queen’s English?
- American English → increasing prestige (politics, science, technology)

American English

- English colonists → Elizabethan English
- Time → language changed on both sides
 - Ex. Loss of ‘r’ before consonants, pauses and end of word → time of revolution
- ‘theory of isolation’ → linguistic conservatism, thus AmEng more conservative than BrEng
- **Archaisms** or **dialectalisms**? Ex.: *mad, fall, gotten, deck, etc*

American English

- Both BrEng & AmEng are equally conservative and/or innovative:

<i>Originally</i>	→	<i>BrEng</i>	/	<i>AmEng</i>
<i>fall</i>		<i>autumn</i>		<i>fall</i>
<i>gotten</i>		<i>got</i>		<i>gotten</i>
<i>waistcoat</i>		<i>waistcoat</i>		<i>vest</i>
<i>fortnight</i>		<i>fortnight</i>		<i>2 weeks</i>

American English

- New words in AmEng:

1. Semantic shift

	<i>BrEng</i>	<i>AmEng</i>
creek	small arm of sea	small stream

2. Compounds

backwoods, underbrush, watergap ...

3. Borrowings

<i>Spanish</i>	<i>French</i>	<i>German</i>	<i>Dutch</i>	<i>Indian</i>
Canyon	prairie	semester	boss	raccoon

AmEng is essentially a **development of 17th c BrEng**

American English

- **Lexical Differences:**

<i>BrEng</i>	<i>AmEng</i>	<i>BrEng</i>	<i>AmEng</i>
<i>post</i>	<i>mail</i>	<i>angry</i>	<i>mad</i>
<i>lugage</i>	<i>baggage</i>	<i>parcel</i>	<i>package</i>
<i>staircase</i>	<i>stairway</i>	<i>coach</i>	<i>bus</i>
<i>cock</i>	<i>rooster</i>	<i>rubber</i>	<i>eraser</i>

American English

- **American influence on BrEng**
 - British speakers → high-handed attitude toward AmEng
 - Americans → greater commercial, technical and political power
 - Sir William Craigie, ex. of ‘Americanisms’ in BrEng:
 - *backwoods, blizzard, caucus, cloudburst, prairie*
 - Recent **Americanisms**:
 - *cafeteria, cocktail, egghead, electrocute, fan, radio (wireless), ok, dj, double talk, show business, star, alibi, know-how, maybe, quit, way of life, right away ...*

American English

- Differences in **Pronunciation**:

- BrEng shift of an older British vowel / **&** / **to** / **a:** / except before r (*far*), lm (*calm*), *father*. This shift also occurs in New England and some parts of the south, it was considered ‘vulgar’ until the 18th in Britain
- AmEng pronunciacion of / ae / - /a:/ is not consistent and an intermediate /**a**/ may also be heard
- AmEng short **o** /**A**/ is **unrounded** → *got*, *God*, *stop* (not consistent)
- Loss of **secondary stress** on the penultimate syllable of polysyllables in ‘-ary’, ‘-ery’, ‘-ory’ in BrEng: *military*, *obligatory* ...
- Different rates in tempo of speech

American English

- Differences in **Spelling**:

AmEng	BrEng	AmEng	BrEng
<i>Check</i>	<i>cheque</i>	<i>pajamas</i>	<i>pyjamas</i>
<i>Cider</i>	<i>cyder</i>	<i>jail</i>	<i>gaol</i>

- **Noah Webster's** innovations:

1. AmEng –or	BrEng. –our
<i>color</i>	<i>colour</i>
<i>behavior</i>	<i>behaviour</i>
<i>neighbor</i>	<i>neighbour</i>

** but BrEng: *author* (no *authour*), *doctor* ...

2. AmEng. –er	BrEng. –re
<i>center</i>	<i>centre</i>
<i>theater</i>	<i>theatre</i>

American English

3. **AmEng. –se**

defense

offense

BrEng. –ce

defence

offence

4. **AmEng. –c**

music

public

BrEng. –ck > -c

musick > music

publick > public

5. **AmEng –l-**

traveling

traveler

BrEng –ll-

travelling

traveller

American English

- American English **dialects**:
 - Use of English depends on:
 - Place (regional / geographical dialects)
 - Culture (ethnic / social)
 - Others: sex, age, education, etc
 - **3 or 4 main AmEng dialects in Eastern part**:
 - **Northern** (New Jersey to New England)
 - **North Midland** (Delaware to Pennsylvania)
 - **South Midland / Inland Southern** (W. Virginia to Georgia)
 - **Southern / Coastal Southern** (Delaware to Florida)
 - West America → **GA** = General American
 - 1889 → foundation of the American Dialect Society

American English

1. General American – GA

- **Rhotic** variety: retroflex ‘r’
- **vowel o** is unrounded in contrast with BrEng o:
God, pot
- **no long a** /a:/ in GA (except in Northeast): *half, park, calm*
- Because of **rhoticity**, some RP diphthongs and vowels do not occur in AmEng: *dear, dare, tour, bird*
- Intervocalic /t/ for t & d, homophonous: *metal / medal, winter / winner*
- No i-glide /j/ in words like *duke, tuna, news*
- Nasal twang

American English

2. **Northeastern** accent

- New England
- sounds partly like BrEng
- non-**rhotic** variety
- have vowel /a:/ in calm, father, park, etc
- have rounded and unrounded vowel /o/

3. **Southern** accent

- generally non-rhotic accents
- more relaxed
- pronoun *y'all* (*you all*)
- diphthong /ai/ is often a monophthong: *high* /ha:/

American English

- **Ethnic and Social dialects:**
 - **Labov:** ‘The Social stratification of English in New York city’, 1966 → Sociolinguistics
 - American ethnic groups: Blacks, Appalachians, Jews, Chicanos, Puerto Ricans, Penn Dutch, Asians, etc
 - Linguistic diversity in classroom → major problem in US 20c education
 - ‘**melting pot**’: problems of AmEng:
 - Linguistic diversity against Anglo-Americans
 - Risk of balkanization of America

American English

• African American English:

- 2 important issues:
 - *How differently Black and White Americans speak?*
 - *What is the origin of Black English?*
- 2 theories:
 - Black English is a separate language (BEV) → ‘Eubonics’
 - Differences are often exaggerated → same language
- Black contribution to AmEng.:
 - Lexical: *nitty-gritty, jazz, jam ...*
 - Pronunciation: drop t in *rest, soft ...*
 - Grammar: consuetudinal be (*She be here everyday*), absence of be (*She here now*)
- **Origin**, 2 theories:
 - Blacks picked up English from Whites on the plantations of the New World (African infl.)
 - Blacks → **pidgin** → creolized

Canadian English

Canadian English

- World's **2nd largest** country
- **Pop.:** 28 million approx. (300,000 Indians in reservations, canada → Iroquois *kanata* = village)
- Head of state: Queen Elizabeth II (England), represented by governor general
- Federal constitutional monarchy
- ½ its pop. live in Ontario and Quebec (**80%** urban pop.!!!)
- **Languages:** English (70%, Protestants), French (20%, Catholic), bilingual (10%), others (**Inuktitut** by Inuit).

Canadian English

Canadian English

Canadian English

- Canadian English: 3 main **accents**:

1. General Canadian
2. Maritime
3. Newfie (Newfoundland)

1. General Canadian

- Similar to GA (western US English)
- Most typical feature: **Canadian raising**
ex.: *Are you Spanish, eh?*
- Unlike GA, CanEng has /ou/ in words such as *borrow*, *sorrow*

Canadian English

2. Maritime

- Spoken in Prince Edward Island, Nova Scotia & New Brunswick
- No Canadian raising (‘*eh?*’)

3. Newfie (Newfoundland)

- No Canadian raising
- Sounds sometimes like Irish English or South-west English accent → ‘**Hiberno-English**’

Canadian English

- **Canadian English:**
 - **Spelling:** controversy **BrEng.** Vs. **AmEng** ('serious' press and academic books tend to follow British spelling: *centre, programme*, etc)
 - **Vocabulary** (typical Canadian words): borrowed from 2 sources:
 1. from **Indigenous** languages (Cree, Inuktitut): *chipmunk, mackinaw, moose, muskeg, muskrat, kayak, anorak, husky, toboggan*, etc
 2. from **French**: *métis* (person of mixed race), *tuque* (cap), *caboteur* (ship), etc

Ireland, Wales & Scotland

Shetland Islands

Orkney Islands

Atlantic Ocean

John O'Groats

Lewis

North Sea

Highlands

Inverness

Skye

Loch Ness

Aviemore

Scotland

Aberdeen

Fort William

Braemar

- 1,000 BC: Picts reached Scotland from Europe
- 843: Unification of Picts, Scots, Britons and Angles under Kenneth I MacAlpine
- **1296**: Edward I of England invaded Scotland and declared himself king
- 1297: William Wallace (**Braveheart**) defeated English
- **1328: Independence of Scotland** recognized by England

Dundee

St Andrews

Stirling

Glasgow

Edinburgh

Kelso

Ireland

Northern Ireland

The Borders

England

- **1707: Act of Union: united England and Scotland parliaments**

SCOTTISH ENGLISH

- Pop.: 5 million approx.
- Langs.: Scots Gaelic & English
- English:
 - **Southeast:** English spoken as far in time as in England
 - **Southwest:** English spoken since Middle Ages
 - **Highlands and Islands:** English spoken only for 2 centuries

Pronunciation:

- Fewer vowels than RP for 2 reasons:
 - **Rhotic** variety, so diphthongs ending in schwa not all present: beer, bear, etc
 - **Scottish vowel Length rule:** vowels are long before /v/, /r/, /z/, /dɒnpalo/, before another vowel and are long elsewhere (esp. affects vowels i and u)
ex.: /i:/ long: *here, leave, sees* ...
/i/ short: *beat, feel, leaf* ...
- velar fricative /x/ in some Scottish words: *loch, nicht*
- Different stress & pronunciation: *realíze, with* (voiceless)

Scotland Council Areas

SCOTTISH ENGLISH

Grammar:

- **will** instead of shall: *Will I put out the light?* (Shall/should?)
- **prepositions** in verbs placed before direct object: *he turned out the light* (the light out), *they took off their coats* (their coats off)

Vocabulary

- *aye* = yes
- *brade* = hill
- *dram* = drink
- *loch* = lake
- *wee* = small
- *to mind* = to remember
- *How are you keeping?* = How are you?
- *I've got the cold* = a cold
- *The back of 9 o'clock* = soon after 9

Shetland Islands

Orkney Islands

Atlantic Ocean

North Sea

Lewis

Highlands

John O'Groats

Inverness

Skye

Scotland

Loch Ness

Aviemore

Aberdeen

Fort William

Braemar

Dundee

St Andrews

Stirling

Glasgow

Edinburgh

Kelso

Ireland

Northern Ireland

The Borders

England

SCOTTISH ENGLISH

Vocabulary:

- ScotEng words present in Standard Eng.:
 - *collie, golf, weird, cosy, glamour, pony, wraith, croon, whisky*
- ScotEng words widely known as typically Scottish:
 - *clan, kilt, cairn, haggis, bairn*
- ScotEng words used only in Scotland (& Ulster):
 - *brae, burn, kirk, canny, kirl*

Atlantic Ocean

Irish English

- **1845-49: FAMINE**
(Ireland's pop 8.5 → 6.5 mil.)
- **1937** Constitution of "Eire"
- **1951-62** IRA campaign in North.
- **1972** Ireland joins the European Economic Community
- **1993** Downing Street Declaration; British Government accepts the right of the people of Ireland to self-determination.
- **1997** IRA cease-fire

Irish English

- Northern and Southern Irish English

Southern Irish Eng.:

Pronunciation:

- rhotic
- words like *hoarse*, *mourning* → /ɝ/ rather than /ou/
- *nurse* is /nurs/ rather than /nɜrs/
- uneducated speech: *tea*, *please*, *sea* → /ei/
- *old*, *cold*, *bold* → /au/
- th sometimes /t/ ex. *thousand*

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Atlantic Ocean

Southern Irish Eng.:

Grammar:

- progressive verbs more frequent: *This is belonging to me*
- diff. use of ‘do’ → habitual / non-habitual: *I am drunk (now) <> I do be drunk (usually)*
- Irish calques: *I’m after seeing him* (I’ve just seen him)
- avoidance of perfect tense: *How long are you here?* (have you been)
- let* sometimes command 2nd person: *let you stay here (stay here!)*

Irish English

- **Vocabulary:**

- afters: dessert
- banjaxed: broken, no good
- The Black Stuff: Guinness
- bollocks: stupid
- boozer: pub
- dry up: Shut up!
- eejit: idiot
- flaming, fluthered, locked: drunk

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Northern Irish English

- **Pronunciation:**

- rhotic

- /ou/ sometimes /oi/ →
know, house ...

- Words like *bird, card* =
USEnglish

- **Grammar:**

- Use of *whenever* for
when: *whenever my baby
was born, I became
depressed*

Welsh English

•Pronunciation:

- unstressed a tends to be /æ/ rather than schwa, ex: *sofa*
- no contrast between schwa and /ʒ/, ex.: *rubber*
- contrast between /ou/ (*nose*) and /ju/ (*knows*)
- non-rhotic except East and South-west
- tendency to make intervocalic consonants longer: *money* /mɛnni/

Welsh English

- **Grammar:**

- Universal tag question 'isnt' it'
- Predicated object inversion for emphasis: *Coming home tomorrow he is*
- Use of negative too: I can't do it, too

- **Vocabulary:**

- language of Wales
→ **Cymraeg**, used by 1/2 million people
- aye: yes ...

Australian & New Zealand English

Australian English

Australian English

Pronunciation:

- **Non-rhotic**, similar to South east of England
- **Long vowel /a:/** in half as in RP
- **Intervocalic /t/ as a flap /d/** in *city* as in USEng
- Speech rhythms are slow
- Use of schwa rather than short i in naked, acid, etc
- No regional differences

Australian English

Vocabulary:

- **Aussie:** Australian slang
 - *larrikin:* hooligan
 - *sheila:* girl
 - *chook:* chicken
 - *chunder:* vomit
 - *stove:* cooker
 - *frock:* dress
 - *paddock:* field
 - *footpath:* pavement
 - *a spell:* a break, rest
 - *go crook at:* angry, mad
 - *dag:* eccentric person

Australian English

- **Aboriginal words:**

- *boomerang*
- *corroboree*: dance
- *jackeroo*: farm manager
- *Kangaroo*
- *kookaburra*: kind of bird
- *emu*: kind of bird
- *koala*
- *wombat*: a marsupial

New Zealand English

Pronunciation:

- non-rhotic, similar to RP (in South island some rhotic speakers of Scottish origin)
- vowels in *ham* and *pen* perceived like ‘hem’, ‘pen’
- centralization of short i to schwa
- Schwa preferred in unstressed syllables
- use of /i:/ in *very*, *many*, etc

New Zealand

Vocabulary:

- *tramping*: hiking
- to *uplift*: to pick up
- to *jack up*: to arrange
- *bach*: a holiday house
- *Offsider*: companion
- From **Maori**:
 - *aroha*: love
 - *waka*: canoe
 - *tangata*: people
 - *mana*: power
 - *manuwhiri*: guest, visitor
 - *cockabully*: a small fish
- From **Samoan**: *fale* (house), *talofa* (a ceremonial greeting), etc

African English

African English

African English

WEST AFRICAN

- Pronunciation:
 - reduced system
 - non-rhotic
 - final –mb with a /b/:
climb, bomb
 - tendency to reduce final clusters: last
/las/, passed /pas/
 - diff. stress:
congratuláte, investigáte, súccess
 - Syllabled-time

African English

- **WEST AFRICAN**
- **Grammar:**
 - depends on area
 - omission of articles: *I'm going to cinema*
 - no distinction between reflexive/reciprocal: *They like themselves* (each other)
 - universal tag question 'is it'
- **Vocabulary:**
 - *balance* (money change)
 - *hear*: understand
 - *to take in*: become pregnant
 - *epistle*: letter
 - *purchase*: buyu

KENYA

African English

EAST AFRICAN

- **Pronunciation:**
 - fewer vowels than in West African
 - many speakers do not distinguish l & r
- **Vocabulary:**
 - many words from indigenous languages: *askari* (policeman), *duka* (shop), *kibanda* (black market), *chai* (tea), *matatu* (bus) ...

African English

- **South African English** (white) sounds like Australian and British English.
- **AFRIKAANS:** South Africa & Namibia → Dutch + English (ex. Agt / eight)
- The English pidgin spoken by **Bantu** mother-tongue South Africans is influenced by intonation and pronunciation of Bantu languages, i.e. **Zulu**

African English

- Vocabulary: *trek*, *veldt*, *apartheid* ...
- Words from Afrikaans & Bantu:
 - oop (open)
 - maak (make)
 - skool (school)
 - ys (ice)
 - ses (six)
 - nege (nine)

INDIAN ENGLISH

INDIAN ENGLISH

Pronunciation:

- varies depending on speaker's native language
- reduced vowel system
- diphthongs /ei/ and /ou/ tend to /e:/ and /o:/
- **Southern India:** word initial front vowels have /j/ and back vowels /w/:
eight /je:t/
- **Northern India:** word initial /sk/, /st/, /sp/ have /i/:
speak /ispi:k/
- Diff. stress, rhythm

INDIAN ENGLISH

• Grammar:

- Pluralization of mass nouns: *fruits, furnitures ...*
- **Diff. use of prepositions:** *to accompany with, to fear of, pay attention on ...*
- diff. use of present tense: *When you **will** arrive, call me*
- **No inversion** in questions: *What this is made from?*
- Universal tag question 'isn't it'

INDIAN ENGLISH

- **Vocabulary**

- Crore: 10 million
- Sahib: sir, master
- Lakh: 100 thousand
- Swadeshi: indigenous

- **In Standard:**

- Bungalow
- Pajamas
- Veranda
- Banyan
- Thug
- Curry
- mango